

D4.1 – BIMprove Impact Master Plan

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D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan

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Abstract

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation are vital elements of any successful H2020 funded project. The present document presents a detailed overview of **BIMprove's** strategy while defining the goals, priorities and any potential implementation mechanisms to achieve all desirable outcomes. To this end, **BIMprove's Impact Master Plan** sets out the objectives, tools, materials, and channels to be exploited in order to effectively spread **BIMProve's** activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences, also becoming the cornerstone for the successful commercialization and market uptake of **BIMProve** solution.

Keywords

Digital Twins, BIM, Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, Standardization, Agile, Impact, Building Information Modelling

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
BIM	Building Information Modelling
AR	Augmented Reality
VR	Virtual Reality
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
RTD	Research and Technical (or Technological) Development
BCF	BIM Collaboration Format
HSE	Health, Safety and Environment
SDO	Standards Developing Organization

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that BIMprove system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Research innovation is a driving force for economic growth, the creation of new job opportunities and the enhancement of the standard of living. It is therefore important to ensure that the knowledge generated within research and innovation projects is properly diffused and that the means through which such knowledge can be delivered to the society are being effectively explored. This is realized through the commercial exploitation of products and services, which is the primary way of delivering research results to the citizens (end-users). In addition, communicating research results can effectively accelerate research and technical development (RTD) towards increasing the technology readiness level (TRL), going beyond the current state of the art, and even creating new research horizon lines on future and emerging trends. Furthermore, dissemination activities, such as participation in workshops or publication of information in websites, enable participants “to get feedback on the economic potential and recommended market-oriented exploitation pathways”.¹

The current document outlines the initial **BIMprove Impact Master Plan** consisting of the overall project dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies including an extensive overview of the standardization landscape in the area of BIM and will be the basis for further standardization activities in the project.

The plan is the result of a coordinated effort among partners, considering stakeholders’ categories and needs as well as partners’ communication channels and tools. In this sense, it is a supporting tool for each partner in maximizing the impact of their own dissemination actions while providing means to ensure high visibility of activities and outcomes of the project as a whole. This plan proposes a list of suitable communication & dissemination tools and activities for engaging the target groups in the project. To this end, a multi-step and multi-channel dissemination strategy is proposed in order to maximize the impact of the dissemination activities, adjusting the materials and tools to the specific needs, interests and potential for involvement of the target audience.

The consortium considers this plan as a living document, reflecting an open, ongoing dialogue with potential users and related networks during the project, in order to be inclusive and to ensure the best possible results.

¹ D6.1: Dissemination and Exploitation Plan and Annual Dissemination Report 1 (31/08/2017), ICARUS Project, Retrieved from: <https://icarus-alloys.eu/>

2. AGILE STAKEHOLDER MANAGEMENT

2.1. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

Identifying and engaging with the most relevant stakeholders is an activity often referred to as 'community building' and it is a key aspect of every H2020 project, such as **BIMprove**. Indeed, the programme relies on communities, initiatives and projects that will either use the outcomes or relate and possibly liaise with its activities along its course.

Creating and nurturing an ecosystem of key players around an initiative is always a crucial factor in the outcomes and success of its value stream. The stakeholder's impact on a project depends on its potential power -the ability to influence the value proposition- and the interest in exercising that power. Assessing the relative levels of each supports the decision on whom to spend time and effort to realize the greatest benefits.

When it comes to addressing fundamental challenges in Research and Innovation, multiple initiatives often work in a standalone manner to address the same issue from multiple directions, incurring in inefficiencies and being incapable of delivering their full potential. By adopting an open framework of collaboration with peers and groups that can benefit and contribute to the impact of the project, **BIMprove** will be able to reach a deeper understanding of the requirements and benefits from aligning efforts with similar task forces as it requires a responsive growth factor capable of prospecting and creating brand new synergies over the project's lifetime, facilitating a greater advantage and extending its range of action.

2.1.1. ENGAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

To maximise the effectiveness of the dissemination, communication & exploitation plans that will be introduced in this document, the consortium requires a mechanism for managing in a systematic manner the ever-changing list of organisations, initiatives and players with a position to influence the value streams of the project.

For this reason, **BIMprove** will implement an **Agile Stakeholder Engagement** framework, designed to continuously developing and strengthening relationships with a significant audience through the values of the **Agile Manifesto**²:

² <http://agilemanifesto.org/>

Table 1: Agile Manifesto Principles

The Agile Manifesto Principles		
Individuals and interactions	over	processes and tools
Results	over	comprehensive documentation
Collaboration	over	formality
Responding to change	over	following a plan

- **Individuals and interactions over processes and tools:** Ecosystem building is a team-based approach to deliver value as a joint effort. Tools are an important part of projects, but the team needs to work together effectively through productive interactions with the stakeholders.
- **Results over comprehensive documentation:** It is much more valuable to interact with the stakeholders, obtaining continuous feedback and managing increments of the ecosystem’s snapshot rather than overspending resources in studying and reporting about their profiles and potential objectives.
- **Collaboration over formality:** This framework is designed to promote and facilitate collaboration in the programme. The team aims to engage and collaborate with stakeholders to inspect and adapt the vision, so the project will be as valuable as possible.
- **Responding to change over following a plan:** Rather than maintaining a fully defined and static vision of the stakeholders from the project, this methodology focuses on building up an ecosystem of interested parts throughout its lifetime.

The framework follows an iterative implementation structure based on **Sprints**, time-boxes of 6 months where the main goal is to incrementally increase and reinforce the engagement of the stakeholders with the initiative. A new Sprint starts immediately after the conclusion of the previous Sprint at the end of each quarter of the project (Sprint Qx). Its workflow includes the following phases:

Figure 1: Stakeholder Engagement Framework

- **Phase 1 – Scouting:** Building upon the objectives of **BIMprove** and the findings from previous Sprints, this phase will explore, map and assess Target Groups -and specific candidates- with different degrees of relevance for the scope and impact of the work plan. **BIMprove** will build upon the sound experience and active involvement of the consortium members in initiatives and players that must be considered as baseline for engagement, taking advantage of new leads generated by second-degree partnerships and new opportunities as outcome of the Interaction phase, including emerging PPPs and H2020 projects. The key result will be a version of the ‘Stakeholder Map’, a graphical instrument to 1) list key actors -and specific candidates within them; 2) thoughtfully organise and correlate these audiences; 3) define a common terminology to be used in all the project’s reference.
- **Phase 2 – Interaction:** Next stage will imply the interaction as such with the identified target groups, supporting the activities outlined in the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies. This is the phase where **BIMprove** will collaborate with initiatives having a specific mandate on industrial digitisation. Whenever relevant, the project will formally join specific Task Forces and Working Groups, contribute to scientific publications and participate in events. Feedback extrapolated from previous Sprints will be used to enhance the efficiency and impact of these measures;
Phase 3 – Learning: From the actions performed during the interaction, the consortium will learn lessons and collect findings that will feed the next Sprint. This will also include insights obtained from consultation (e.g. in the form of quick questionnaires or interviews), gathering valuable external remarks about the project and its operation.

2.1.2. TARGET AUDIENCE & STAKEHOLDERS

Promoting **BIMprove** and encouraging stakeholders to engage with the initiative requires understanding who the ‘target audience’ is. Understanding these profiles and their influence in the value chain is essential to craft the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plans.

Figure 2: BIMprove's Target Audience

- **Construction Industry:** This group includes a number of actors and individuals who are at the heart of the construction industry value chain, such as the site owner, the construction manager and specialty contractors, the construction labour force, the material and equipment supplier and other. The current group outlines the beneficiaries in terms of productivity, resource efficient management and safety of applying digital twin technologies to the construction sector. The involvement of different actors from the value chain will be extremely meaningful to **BIMprove** when it comes to 1) obtaining integrated requirements and feedback to support the implementation of the project, understanding internal processes, risk allocation and sustainability as a whole, reducing the effect of the fragmented nature of this industry; 2) facilitating access to the data collection; and 3) raising awareness on the potential advantages the deployment and operation of digital twin creates in real-world scenarios.
 - **Owner:** one who has the legal right or title to a piece of property.
 - **Client:** entity, individual or organisation commissioning and funding the project, directly or indirectly (Main role in design phase)
 - **Facility manager:** ensures functionality, comfort, safety and efficiency of the built environment by integrating people, place, process and technology. (For operation phase)

- **Project manager:** plans and oversee construction projects from beginning to end. Hires subcontractors and works with engineers and architects as needed, and keeping track of an inventory of equipment and materials.
 - **Site manager (or construction manager):** is overall responsible person for the project construction management at the construction site. The site manager is required to keep within the timescale and budget of a project, and manage any delays or problems encountered on site during a construction project.
 - **BIM manager (or BIM coordinator):** A great part of Improves the tasks includes the support of less experienced personnel in BIM technology as well as model and data management on the project. Also responsible for contacting designer and guaranteeing right quality digital design documentation. Such a person is also a link between the design office and the construction site. Her/his task is to maintain a good level of communication, which is mostly carried out by using .ifc models. She/he also prepare well-written contract with the designer, including the execution of the project with the use of BIM technology.
 - **Surveyor:** works within construction on the measurement and monitoring of projects, as well as producing maps, plans and charts of different features. When construction workers are unsure about the data in the model, or whether taken dimensions are correct, they often ask surveyors to mark and check, for instance, construction points or from work. Surveyor' is a very broad term that covers a wide range of disciplines and activities.
 - **Planner engineer:** works with the construction technology and time schedule. She/he models and understand all the subsequent phases of the construction, creating 4D.
 - **Quality engineer:** an employee working in this position is responsible for archiving it in the system or directly in the BIM model, assigning documents to the specific elements.
 - **Tender engineer:** handles data needed to prepare a tender of the project.
 - **Health and safety specialist:** such a person can notice possible risks and dangers and then pass them on in an accessible and understandable form to the employees.
 - **Foreman:** construction worker or skilled tradesperson who is in charge of a construction crew. This role is generally assumed by a senior construction worker
 - **Construction worker:** a worker employed in manual labour of the physical construction
 - **Project controller:** a person working in this position must know, among other things, how the data and documentation management system works or where to find the current status of the project.
- **Digital Twin Technology Providers:** The second stakeholder group includes technology providers such as Large Tech Industries, Tech SMEs/ start-ups, Universities & RTOs,

Standardization Organizations and others, who are responsible for developing and delivering digital twin related technology to the construction industry.

- **Large industry:** large technology companies are investing billions all over the world in R&D and acquisitions in an attempt to lead the AI field. Some of them are actively participating in initiatives to address the social impacts of AI, with healthcare as the market of greatest deal flow;
- **Technology small providers:** although with fewer resources to invest, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and start-ups accumulate up to 98% of the construction chain. Digitisation of SMEs in the construction sector is strategic for the EU;
- **Data brokers/ aggregators:** data brokers operate in the shadows of the Internet and most consumers are unaware or unsure how to put restrictions on their activity. **BIMprove** will put emphasis to develop a narrative for an ethical and transparent use of good-quality data, fostering better practices among smaller entities without access to swathes of user data with the repository of health images envisioned in the scope of the project;
- **Universities and Research Technology Organisations (RTOs):** a large amount of research, development and innovation for AI is taking place on academic organizations. They are a prime source of talent AI of a field that will be shaped by a vast array of academic researchers and data scientists, and not just a handful of corporate giants;
- **Standards Developing Organizations (SDOs):** The construction industry is regulated by a myriad of standards, guidelines, codes of practice and regulations, where formal international standardization for BIM is organized by ISO and on European level by CEN. **BIMprove** will identify and contribute to those bodies and technical committees working in advanced research towards global standards infrastructures from data capturing to advanced knowledge and decisions;
- **Digital Transformation Advocates:** The third and also critical group is dedicated to the initiatives and organizations actively advocating the digitisation of the construction sector, promoting innovation, competitiveness and sustainability, with special focus on SMEs and start-ups, such as the EU BIM Task Group, the European Construction Industry Federation, the European International Contractors association, National and International Green Building Councils and others.
 - **[EU BIM Task Group](#)** – A pan-European approach of public procurers, policy makers and public estate owners to encourage the common use of BIM, as ‘digital construction’, in public works. The group published a handbook to facilitate the use of BIM by the European public sector across 21 countries⁵;

- **European construction associations** – private organisations representing the interests from their members -often from the industry- and facilitating prospects and road maps of the sector. The [European Construction Industry Federation](#) is structured in 32 national member federations, that is in charge of the “[Construction 4.0 Working Group](#)” to follow relevant policy developments, inform member federations and select priority issues for more in-depth research and discussion. Other initiatives include the [European International Contractors](#) and the [Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction](#) – the mission by the United Nations Environment Programme as a catalyst to encourage "greater pace and impact of climate action in the buildings and construction sector";
- **Green Building Councils** – non-profit organisations made up of businesses and organisations working in the construction of ‘green buildings’, that, in its design, construction or operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on our climate and natural environment;
- [Enterprise Europe Network](#) – one of the most relevant networks for supporting innovative SMEs in Europe, with 600+ active member organisations in 60+ countries worldwide;
- **Digital Innovation Hubs** – pan European network of one - stop - shops that help companies to become more competitive with regard to their business/production processes, products or services using digital technologies.
- **H2020 Funded Projects:** Other H2020 EU funded projects, operating and researching in the same domain as BIMprove are also a key stakeholder group which the project will seek to create active synergies. Projects funded under the LC-EEB-08-2020, LC-EEB-07-2020, LC-EEB-04-2020 calls of proposal will be on the main frame, however other projects from previous call of proposals (such as LC-EEB-2018 and 2019) or domains will be also reached.
- **Policy Makers:** Members of a government department, legislature, or other organizations responsible for making new policies and for promoting strategies responsible for buildings and energy, are also a vital part of the value chain. National/Regional policy makers for buildings & energy, Regulators, Local governments and others, cannot be left outside the equation and are a key part of **BIMprove**’s engagement target.
- **The Society:** The general public should not be overlooked. It is crucial to inform the public about the benefits that digital transformation brings to the construction industry, incentivizing a low-carbon strategy towards the world’s largest consumer of raw materials, and constructed objects account for between 25 and 40 percent of total carbon emissions in the world.

2.2. STAKEHOLDERS MAP

Figure below contains the first version of the **BIMProve** Stakeholders Map, that graphically summarises all the target audiences at this stage. Such diagram has been defined by taking into consideration the different target stakeholders' groups identified so far, as the outcome of, the ongoing, Sprint Q1 of the Agile Stakeholder Framework. A more detailed mindmap can be found in **ANNEX 1: Stakeholders Mindmap**.

Figure 3: Stakeholders Map

3. DISSEMINATION& COMMUNICATION

Dissemination in Research and Innovation Projects is a key and necessary element for achieving the desired impact of the project. According to the European Commission, *“Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers). By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.”*³

3.1. DISSEMINATION PLAN

To this end, **BIMprove** has developed a flexible and adjustable Dissemination Plan that aims on building effective awareness of the project results, creating understanding and aiming for action among the key target audience identified. The execution of this strategy will facilitate the best use and uptake of the outcomes and research insights generated throughout the project lifetime, reinforcing each of the impacts aimed in the work plan.

3.1.1. “3 PHASES” APPROACH

Dissemination activities will be carried out in **three main phases**. Each of these has specific objectives and will therefore perform specific actions using appropriate channels. These phases will be presented and discussed at the beginning of the project and will be refined accordingly to match the priorities of **BIMprove**.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

Figure 4: Dissemination Plan Phases

- Phase I: Analysis (M01-M06).** In this preliminary phase, the Consortium will analyse the project's framework, with a special attention to internal and external barriers and obstacles that could slow down the dissemination activities, as well as it will define the priorities and actions for the first year of the project. The Dissemination & Communication Leader will coordinate the engagement activities, to align the dissemination activities with the needs of the stakeholders identified, creating general awareness about the project's objectives and expected results. During this phase, a first set of promotional material, produced in the frame of BIMprove communication plan will be prepared and delivered.
- Phase II: Increase impact (M06-M18).** The main objective of Phase II is to increase impact and awareness generated during Phase I and to expose mainly the BIMprove achievements. The Dissemination & Communication Leader will adapt the channels and measures identified in the proposal phase (and refined during Phase I) to the specific needs of Phase II, and it will work to properly find the right means to engage and collaborate with the target groups. This will help increase the potential impact of the project's results. Participation in workshops, organisations of ad hoc events, as well as organisation of tutorials/webinars (if needed) will boost the dissemination process. Specific PR material will be also produced.
- Phase III: Adoption (M18-M36).** This phase will leverage the general awareness raised in Phase I and Phase II, attracting more potential users and customers of BIMprove project's results. The Dissemination & Communication Leader together

with the Exploitation Leader will evaluate the outcomes of Phase I and II and, if needed, it will refine the priorities, channels and measures previously settled, also in concertation with the agile stakeholder management activities. Secondly, it will define the main activities that could increase the impact also beyond the project's lifetime, such as continuing use of events, participation in workshops and conferences, contributions to publications in targeted specific media online and printed trade and research journals.

3.1.2. OBJECTIVES

The main and key objectives of the dissemination strategy are as follows:

- To set up the information dissemination mechanisms and priorities of **BIMprove**;
- To establish, maintain and grow a community around **BIMprove** in coordination with the stakeholder management framework;
- To create visibility and promote the work and results for target stakeholders by creating promotional material and information campaigns;
- To disseminate project and outcomes to the widest possible community through various channels and instruments. External participation and knowledge sharing will be encouraged through networking activities and events aimed at increasing the impact potential and enriching the contribution to the project;
- To conduct liaison with other EU, national and international initiatives to maximise the impact.

3.1.3. MEASURES

In order to execute the dissemination plan, the consortium was identified a number of measures that need to be implemented throughout the project, enabling to reach the above-mentioned objectives, in the most efficient and effective way.

Table 2: Dissemination Material

MATERIAL			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
Project Documentation	Documentation material in the form of public deliverables will be made available through BIMprove's public repository ⁴ , as well as CORDIS ⁵ , and	Publicly available information which can be disseminated and infused to similar to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Twin Technology Providers

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/bimprove/?page=1&size=20>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/>

MATERIAL			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
	communicated through our communication channels.	BIMprove initiatives and to the community as a whole.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Advocates • H2020 Funded Projects • Policy Makers
Peer-reviewed Publications	BIMprove aims at publishing and contributing to peer-reviewed publications in top refereed scientific journals and conferences relevant for digital construction. As a RIA project, one of the primary objectives is to ensure the technical achievements and experimental findings of the project will be known and exploited by a larger research community and related scientific domains.	Disseminate the outcomes of the project to a wide scientific community. Showcasing outcomes makes available to the scientific community for further exploitation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Twin Technology Providers • H2020 Funded Projects
Technical Publications	BIMprove consortium, the project will publish and contribute to technical blogs and articles or any other reference from technology providers (bottom-up), as well as references related to the use case application domains under consideration (top-down).	Technical articles can disseminate the project's views and outcomes to a wider scientific and technical audience, leveraging project's impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Twin • Technology Providers • H2020 Funded Projects

Table 3: Dissemination Channels

ONLINE CHANNELS			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
Open Access Library	Following the principle 'as open as possible', BIMprove will provide open access to peer-reviewed publications and scientific research data, following the Data Management Plan. BIMprove is using Zenodo ⁶ OpenAIRE+ ⁷ repository, where it is possible to deposit both publications and data, while providing tools to link them. The Zenodo infrastructure is also used a	"Open Access" Scientific & Technical material allows a wider dissemination of the project's outcome to a wider scientific and technological community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Twin Technology Providers • H2020 Funded Projects

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

ONLINE CHANNELS			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
	document repository for all public deliverables.		
Feedback	BIMprove will set up online measures such as surveys and opinion polls among actors in the key application sectors and the Internet Ecosystem to gather feedback about critical issues of the project, such as validation of priorities and execution of services.	Being able to collect feedback and input from external stakeholders, not only allows you to expand the project's horizons and scope but also to disseminate the project's outcome to a specialised audience.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Policy Makers

Table 4: Dissemination Events (Types)

EVENTS			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
Conferences/ Workshops/ Trade Fairs	The consortium will disseminate outcomes achieved by the project in the form of presentations, talks and personal engagement. This action will include events directly related to BIM, but also end use-oriented affairs with a focus on digital transformation.	Participating in conferences, workshops and trade fairs is a strategic mechanism to interact actively with multiple stakeholders at a time.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders
Exhibition/ Demo Spaces	As an initiative targeting applied technology, one of the objectives of the project is to showcase and validate in public the outcomes achieved. Hence, BIMprove will include in the plan some exhibition activities and demos to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed capabilities.	Showcasing the project's tangible outcomes through exhibitions and demo events, allows the dissemination of concrete outcomes to a wider audience.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders

3.1.3.1 Events List

The list below is an indicative list of events that have identified as main targets. This list is continuously updated by all project partners while actions per event and per partner are being identified and assigned, depending on the maturity of the project. It is also crucial to mention that a lot of events (if not all of them) are transforming to virtual (from physical) as a consequence of the current Covid-19 emergency. In any case, **BIMprove** will seek to get involved regardless the form of the event.

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Table 5: Events List

Event	Type of Event	Date	Location	Short Description
BAU 2021	Trade Fair	13-15.01.21	Munich (Hybrid)	World's Leading Trade Fair for Architecture, Materials and Systems. BIMprove could be represented together with other Fraunhofer projects/activities, but also together with other partners from the consortium.
BIM World Conference	Conference	25-25.11.20	Paris (Digital)	Brings together the entire BIM ecosystem, with 12K participants and 350 exhibitors. The congress focuses on three tracks: Construction 4.0, Property as a Service and Smart Infrastructure
BIMEXPO	Conference	4-7.5.21	Madrid	The leading European Trade Show for BIM Solutions, Services, Networking and Knowledge
European BIM Summit	Conference	22-23.4.21	Barcelona	The purpose is to create synergies with agencies and administrations that are willing to foster a new way of doing things in the construction trade by spreading information and with the cooperation and collaboration of all the stakeholders involved.
EuroXR	Conference	25-27.11.20	Valencia (Virtual)	Europe's leading conference on Virtual Reality (and also Augmented and Mixed Reality). BIMprove will be presented via a Application Poster focused on User Interfaces.
Hannover Messe	Conference	12-16.4.21	Hannover	World's leading trade show for industrial technology addressing core areas of industry and trends, such as Industry 4.0.
InfraBIM Open	Conference	7-9.6.21	Lyon	First and most unique open BIM event in the world, organised by BuildingSmart Finland, with 500+ participants from 25 countries.
ISH Frankfurt	Conference	22-26.3.21	Frankfurt (Digital)	World's leading trade fair focusing on the responsible management of water and energy in buildings, with over 190K visitors and 2,500 exhibitors
Sustainable Places	Conference	27-30.10.20	Digital	Results of EU projects on innovation for the built environment and discussion on topics such as circular economy, digital twins,

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Event	Type of Event	Date	Location	Short Description
				BIPV, local energy communities, sustainable digital infrastructure.
The buildingSMART International Virtual Summit	Conference	26.10-6.11.20	Digital	The buildingSMART International Virtual Summit is now underway for its 2nd online event in 2020. This extended program includes Opening Plenary, Room Sessions, Program and Partners Plenary, Chapter Conference and much more. There are exhibitor booths, personal profiles, networking, and an extensive agenda spanning all phases and domains of the built asset industry. Don't miss out; be part of this unique and global event and participate as a valued member of the community.

3.1.3.2 Conference and Journals List

The following list introduces some of the conferences and journals that the project will emphasise on. However, this list is dynamic and gets updated in a frequent basis according to the scientific and technical maturity of the project.

Table 6: Conferences & Journals List

Event	Type	Date	Location
IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics - Mechatronics and Automation for Construction	Journal	Not relevant	Not relevant
International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction	Scientific Conference	2021 t.b.d	Virtual
CIB W78 – Information Technology for Construction	Scientific Conference	2021 t.b.d	Virtual
International Society for Computing in Civil and Building Engineering (ISCCBE)	Scientific Conference	2021 t.b.d	Virtual

3.2. COMMUNICATION PLAN

Communication in Research and Innovation projects, is «*a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures to communicate to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange*»⁸.

In the case of the **BIMprove** project, Communication activities involve specific measures for promoting the project itself and the results attained. The communication plan has the mission to reach out to a broader audience, beyond the project's core community.

Figure 5: EC's Communication Principles⁹

Figure 6: The Marketing Mix

The plan herein has the mission to reach out to the broadest audience possible. Communication campaigns will be implemented throughout the project lifetime to efficiently build traction among the target audience, emphasising on **BIMprove's technological innovations and pilots' activities**. Such campaigns will build upon the **Promotion Mix** -the fourth element of the **Marketing Mix**¹⁰- that focuses on creating awareness and persuading the audience to initiate the engagement. In the particular case of BIMprove, this

⁸https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/section/communication-toolkit#3%20-%20social%20media>

¹⁰ <https://neilpatel.com/blog/4-ps-of-marketing/>

Promotion Mix is the integration of **Personal Selling, Digital Marketing, Promotional Material and Branding**.

3.2.1. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the communication strategy are as follows:

- Set up internal communication mechanisms among the partners of the consortium;
- Support the external promotion of BIMprove and its outcomes, managing the branding;
- Deliver top level messages about the project to all identified and relevant stakeholders;
- Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of BIMprove and its application in pilot activities;
- Increase awareness and interest about the project.

3.2.1.1 COMMUNICATION MESSAGES PER STAKEHOLDER GROUP

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	MAIN DIRECTIONS OF MESSAGES
Construction Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How the outcomes of the project will help them in their everyday operations. - What is the innovation of the project? - Increase the use of ICT technologies in the Construction industry.
Digital Twin Technology Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the innovation of the project; - How this can be used and further exploited. - Open access of project results.
Digital Advocates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the innovation of the project? - How can the project contribute to standards?
H2020 Funded Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the innovation of the project? - How can we establish a fruitful and beneficial collaboration? - How can we contribute to standards?
Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How ICT affects the Construction sector. - How standards affect the Construction sector.
The Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the innovation of the project; - How this can be used and further exploited; - Open access of project results.

3.2.2. MEASURES

A series of measures and communication tools will be implemented in order to allow the project to reach the right audiences in a communication friendly and to synchronous way. At this point it is important to highlight that all communication tools will be reported in **D4.2 Outreach Material**, to be submitted in Month 6, and are not part of this deliverable.

Table 7: Communication - Personal Selling

PERSONAL SELLING			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
Email Campaigns	Implementing targeted email campaigns to stakeholders for raising awareness about the projects and its activities.	Broadcasting messages to a target pool of contact points via email is a highly effective measure of engagement, especially when promoting activities and outcomes among different ecosystems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Twin Technology Providers • Digital Advocates • H2020 Funded Projects
One-to-one Phone Calls & Meetings	Follow up activity with targeted stakeholders to engage them into future activities and maintain a constant communication flow.	Although this is not a scalable mechanism, one-to-one phone calls and meetings are successful when targeting very specific key actors, often as a follow-up of an email campaign or an event. For the scope of the project, this is especially relevant when engaging members of the Construction Industry and Digital Transformation Advocates with access to their networks.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Advocates
DIGITAL MARKETING			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
Project Website	Establish online presence – website where general public and interested individuals can read about the project progress and findings, including news, articles and public deliverables.	Project website is a key instrument for enhancing visibility of the project, introducing visitors to BIMprove’s rationale and educates them about the project concept. All project findings are published on the website to allow anyone interested in the subject to follow the progress of the project while optimising website optimizes BIMprove on the search engines.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders
Social Media	BIMprove will create and maintain actively its presence in a number of social media channels, with particular focus on Twitter	Social media are fast, low cost channels of reaching interest groups and communities that are	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders

DIGITAL MARKETING			
<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
	and LinkedIn as they have proven to be the most effective tools when engaging with technology communities.	normally not present at any events or conferences (physical or digital).	
Newsletters	Complementary to email engagement, online newsletters will provide a snapshot of the main activities and achievements of. The project will pursue contributing to other Newsletters by the European Commission or associated initiatives. Professional marketing platforms (e.g. MailChimp) will be used to automate the distribution among all contact points	Project newsletter shows the progress of the project to all stakeholders and keeps their interest high	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Twin Technology Providers • Digital Advocates • H2020 Funded Projects
Press Releases	BIMprove will develop and distribute press releases to mainstream and specialist media as well as relevant civil society newsletters, magazines and journals. Press releases will be also distributed individually by partners to communicate the project to their network of customers, members and collaborators.	Within the Communication tactic, press releases can also target specific stakeholders depending on the journal/paper/website where the press release is published or distributed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders
Slide Decks & One Pagers	Design Digital Slide Decks and One-Pagers, for sharing the communication the vision of the project with specialised audiences.	Digital slide decks and one-pagers, often integrated with email campaigns, may replace in some cases the website as 'Point of Market Entry'.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry • Digital Twin Technology Providers • Digital Advocates • H2020 Funded Projects
General Spreading	Publish online articles to various international platforms (i.e. Cordis, Medium, etc,) and on national/local portals, to leverage the BIMprove's scope and results.	Creating and deploying a number of articles in several online media targets at shaping a communication globe around the web sphere to maximise the outreach of the project's results and scope to all stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders
EU BUILD UP Portal	BIMprove will seek to establish synergies with the EU Build Up Portal , for		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction Industry

DIGITAL MARKETING

<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
	utilising its communication facilities including webinars; video, tool, publication libraries; case study database; and EEB networking.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Twin Technology Providers • H2020 Funded Projects

PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL (printed or digital)

<u>Measure</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Benefit of the Measure</u>	<u>Stakeholders</u>
Printed Material	The most common items include brochures, catalogues, posters and any other laid out paper-based resource. Most of the PR material will be available as e-documents and printing will occur as required (e.g. for events, workshops, etc.). BIMprove will also explore other innovative alternatives to the traditional informative material. Labelled gadgets and merchandise have turned out quite effective means of promoting initiatives among a less specialised audience, while encouraging a more sustainable approach when considering long-lasting items.	Project collateral distributed at various events, conferences, workshops, etc. gain the project visibility with the general public and the national and European media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders
Multimedia Material	The project will produce multimedia material to have a self-explanatory and appealing presentation of the project, leveraging other available distribution channels of promotion (e.g. YouTube, Vimeo). The team will organise a set of video interviews throughout the project to collect inputs, taking advantage of plenary meetings and events of relevance. The final results will be edited to mix such interviews with animations.	Visual content has been always proved to be a very effective mean for communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Stakeholders

3.3. DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION MONITORING

3.3.1. MONITORING STRATEGY

Monitoring and adjusting the Dissemination and Communication plan, in a frequent basis, is a fundamental element of the project's success. Continuous monitoring allows the consortium to correct any possible deviations and improve its effectiveness by applying correction and mitigation measures when needed.

It will also address possible implementation problems and identify whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met. Emphasis is given on the pre-assessment of information needs, on the monitoring frequency and the method of collecting evidence.

The execution and effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is depended to a close monitoring, flexible and prompt response mechanism. Every designed and implement activity will be monitored and evaluated according to its account and closely related to the KPIs (see **ANNEX 2: Dissemination & Communication KPIs**).

Figure 7: Dissemination & Communication Loop

- **Design:** Design is activity based on the Dissemination & Communication Plan and the desired impact;
- **Execute:** Execute according to plan;
- **Monitor:** Closely monitor the activity and collect input and results. Monitoring will be based on a template that is available only to partners through the internal website;
- **Evaluate:** Evaluate the outcomes of the activity in a collaborative way according to the desired targets set in the design phase;
- **Learn:** Learn through this evaluation and try to extract the most valuable outcomes out of it;
- **Adjust:** Absorb findings and lessons learnt adjust the plan accordingly, if needed.

All outcomes and results of the Dissemination and Communication plan will be reported in **D4.3 Dissemination and Communication Interim Report** at Month 18 and **D4.6 Impact Assessment and Exploitation Final Report** at Month 36.

3.3.2. POSSIBLE RISKS

There are a number of risks and potential issues related to the communication and dissemination side of the project. These risks will be monitored and mitigated by the Communication & Dissemination leader who will also control these risks on a regular basis and will report any changes to the Project Coordinator. Examples of communication risks include but are not limited to:

Table 8: Dissemination & Communication Risks

DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION RISKS		
<u>Risk</u>	<u>Priority</u>	<u>Measure to minimise Risk</u>
Covid 19 Impact to dissemination & communication activities (especially physical events)	High	The Covid 19 pandemic is a reality that cannot be overlook, clearly posing a challenge towards dissemination & communication. For this reason, we foresee to implement most of our activities virtually and not with a physical presence, at least for the following months to come. Moreover, we have designed a well structure and inclusive online (social media, website, etc) aiming to ensure that we “stay connected” with our stakeholders. This strategy will be revisited and adjusted when and if necessary.
Communication & Dissemination activities fail to target the correct audiences. The project may fail to draw interest from relevant stakeholders.	High	BIMprove’s partners have defined a clear set of objectives and measures for each target group. However, this agile strategy allows us to revisit and mitigate our activities if needed. Close monitoring and frequent evaluations will make sure that our strategy will remain on track throughout the project.
Lack of public awareness of Project activities	Low	The network is diverse and includes leading scientists, industrial partners, end users, standardization partners, etc. most of them affiliated to international Committees that guarantee relevant connections and channels. If needed, extra budget coming from indirect costs or own resources will be directly allocated to perform any needed foreseen or unforeseen mitigation measures to meet project goals.

4. EXPLOITATION & SUSTAINABILITY

Research and innovation have been placed at the centre of the Europe 2020 strategy to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth. While one can debate what constitutes a healthy relation of industry and basic research, there is no doubt that a knowledge-based society prospers with the innovativeness of its engineers and the skills of its scientists. It is emphasized *that “research is an investment in our future and so put it at the heart of the EU’s blueprint for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth and jobs”*¹¹. For this reason, exploitation is a key ingredient for any H2020 project as it clearly refers to *“the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities”*¹².

The current chapter aims on introducing the initial exploitation plan, to be refined throughout the project, in order to ensure that key findings and lessons learned in this project can help scale up **BIMprove’s** outcomes after the project ends.

4.1. EXPLOITATION PRINCIPLES

In **BIMprove**, exploitation will be tackled in a multidimensional way, aiming to take advantage of all the high-end, innovative outcomes of the project. Different exploitation routes will be examined throughout the project for identifying the most promising exploitation path for each tangible or intangible asset. Figure 8 below, provides a graphical overview of the exploitation path that each exploitable asset will follow throughout the lifetime of the project. Main inspiration for this figure has been the excellent work performed by the HYBUILD project¹³

¹¹ Horizon 2020 - The Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. COM(2011) 808 final, p.2. Retrieved from <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52011DC0808&from=EN>

¹² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

¹³ D7.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan (30/6/2018), HYBUILD H2020 project, Retrieved from: <http://www.hybuild.eu/publications/deliverables/>

Figure 8: BIMprove's Exploitation Path

4.1.1. TECHNOLOGIES & EXPLOITABLE ASSETS

BIMprove project deals with several cutting-edge technologies and technological themes that are instrumental for the future of the construction sector, worldwide. These technologies can be categorised under the following categories:

Figure 9: BIMprove technologies

Following from the above, the following table provides an overview of the **Key Exploitable Results** (KERs) that have been defined in the early stage of the project. However, as the project evolves, an additional or a refined list of exploitable assets will be elaborated.

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Table 9: BIMprove's Exploitable Assets

Tentative KER	Lead partners; IPR (B = Background / F = Foreground)	Exploitation intentions (M=Make/sell U=Use L=License O = Other services/consultancy); Target audience
BIMprove digital thread, cloud-based, layered service framework for AEC industries	SINTEF (B/F) ZHAW (B/F) CATENDA (B/F) HRS (F) VIAS (F) AFG (F)	SINTEF(U/O), ZHAW(U/O), CATENDA(M/U/L), HRS(U), VIAS(U), AFG(U) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large/medium/small construction contractors Cloud Providers Large Technology Providers Technology SMEs / Start-ups
Layer Services, developing / providing open software services for AEC industries	SINTEF (B/F) ZHAW (B/F) CATENDA (B/F) ROBI (B/F)	SINTEF(U/O), ZHAW(U/O), CATENDA(M/U/L), ROBI(M/U/L) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Construction Large Technology providers Technology SMEs / start ups
Robot based automatic / semi-automatic building site tracking services for construction industry	ROBI (B/F) ZHAW (B/F)	ROBI(M/U/L), ZHAW(U/O) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Robot system Integrators Technology providers
BIMprove user notification and HMI services (BIM@Wearable, BIM@Truck, BIM@Anywhere, BIM@Manager)	VTT (B/F) FhG-IAO (B/F) USTUTT (B/F)	VTT(U/L/O), FhG-IAO(U/L/O), USTUTT(U/O) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large/medium/small construction contractors Construction Industry Suppliers
AR/VR representation services of BIM and Digital Twin data for on-site and building office applications	FhG-IAO (B/F) USTUTT (B/F) HRS (F) VIAS (F) AFG (F)	FhG-IAO(U/L/O), USTUTT(U/O), HRS(U), VIAS(U), AFG(U) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large Tech Industry Tech SMEs/ start-ups Data brokers/ aggregators
BIMprove active on-site tracking services of machines and tools for digital asset management and for repair and maintenance	SINTEF (B/F) ZHAW (B/F) CATENDA (B/F) HRS (F) VIAS (F) AFG (F)	SINTEF(U/O), ZHAW(U/O), CATENDA(M/U/L), HRS(U), VIAS(U), AFG(U) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operation & Maintenance providers Construction Machine Service providers Tool providers (HILTI etc.)
BIMprove active on-site tracking services for construction-site safety service providers / municipal fire-brigades etc.	VTT (B/F) HRS (F) VIAS (F) AFG (F)	VTT(U/O), HRS(U), VIAS(U), AFG(U) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal fire-brigades Security services
BIMprove Reference Architecture for AEC industries	DIN (B/F) IINV (F) HRS (F) VIAS (F) AFG (F)	DIN(U/L/O), IINV(O), HRS(U), VIAS(U), AFG(U) Target audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standards Developing Organizations Innovation promoters

4.1.2. KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AND PROTECTION STRATEGY

BIMprove will contemplate three main elements of an effective system to protect and exploit Intellectual Property (IP). Firstly, a system that enables the protection of IP (e.g. patents, copyrights, brand, industrial design) that includes clarity about the ownership and use of IP rights (IPR), the rights and freedom of parties to transfer (assign) IP, and the freedom to publish. Secondly a technology transfer framework, preferably with the support of specialised knowledge transfer offices with professional staff, such as the European IPR Helpdesk . Thirdly a fair law enforcement system in each partner's country that caters for dispute settlement but also that can award penalties and sanctions where appropriate.

Concrete IPR issues have been identified and addressed in the Consortium Agreement. The basic principle is that foreground knowledge, i.e. created within (or resulting from) the project belongs to the project partner who generated it. If knowledge is generated jointly and separate parts cannot be distinguished, it will be jointly owned, unless the contractor concerned agree on a different solution. The granting of Access Rights to jointly owned foreground is royalty-free and the granting of Access Rights to own foreground will is also royalty-free. Regarding background, the granting of Access Rights is royalty-free for the execution of work during the project. For the purposes of policy development and the further promotion of innovation, the European Community has been given a non-exclusive royalty-free license to use the public knowledge generated in the project, e.g. reports, methodologies or case material. Confidential information relating to individuals or companies will be collected and protected in strict accordance with EU and national regulations and best practice regarding data confidentiality. Training material and tutorials are protected by copyright but are being distributed under the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0** International Public License. As a basic principle, licenses to training and coaching material developed or used within **BIMprove** are non-exclusive and non-revocable. Any work or copies of the licensed material may continue to be used under that license.

4.1.3. EXAMPLES OF POTENTIAL BIMPROVE SERVICES

The following two examples are meant to give associations to what can be developed in the **BIMprove** project - so that an understanding of how the project's result can be exploited is less abstract.

4.1.3.1 *BIMprove Product Example 1*

Service: Realtime Progress tracker

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4.1.3.1.1 Value proposition

An “up to date field progress” tracker, where the scans of the construction project is measured up against the information in the BIM¹⁴ models. Deviations to the progress information embedded in the BIM model is flagged via the BCF¹⁵ issues format. The BCF issues are then read by a client BCF server embedded in the scheduling or planning software. This real time feedback loop gives a more accurate view of the real progress of the project.

Figure 10: BIMprove Product example 1

4.1.3.2 BIMprove Product Example 2

Service: Realtime HSE¹⁶ tracker

4.1.3.2.1 Value proposition

Drone/Robots will scan the construction site and create point cloud scans of the areas. The service will recognize points of interests where potential HSE issues may be flagged. The flagged issues are recorded in the BCF format, and sent to the BCF server in the BIM collaboration platform. Other

¹⁴ Building information modelling

¹⁵ BIM Collaboration Format

¹⁶ Health, Safety and Environment

sensor data that is connected to the BIM models will give enhanced overview and information of the physical area being monitored. By correlating real time scan data, sensor data and BIM model data, the users will be able to have an accurate overview of the situation. This real time feedback loop gives a real time view of potential HSE issues in the project.

4.1.3.3 Workflow Example

Each morning the project leader (or delegate) gets a report about the status of HSE issues, progress and geometric deviations. This can be as BCFs so that decisions can be made, and with links so that getting further information is possible. For instance, it is detected that an opening in the security railing was 10 centimetres larger than what can be allowed. It is determined that this has high priority to change, and that the decision is to assign someone to fix this immediately. These reports - and the decisions - can over time be viewed in a report so that change over time can be measured inside and between projects.

4.1.4. TARGET GROUPS

We will be targeting 2 potential categories of stakeholders for our offerings, which are the “potential commercial customer” (Construction Industry and Digital Twin Tech Providers) and the “other target groups”. This is a relevant separation, since estimations of willingness to pay will be different for potential customers compared with for other target groups.

Figure 11: Exploitation Target Groups

4.1.5. MARKET DOMAINS

In the following, a short list is presented of known types of existing offerings in the market. It is not meant to be complete but give an initial overview. These existing products have similarities with what BIMprove will offer, but there are key differences and in most cases the tools can only do one of the things listed.

Table 10: Types of existing products in the market

Scan to BIM	Tools that generate BIM from 3D-scans
Scan vs BIM	Tools that compare 3D-scans vs BIM.
Health & Safety reporting	Software to plan and to follow up safety deviations
Progress tracking	Software to track and report to what degree progress is as scheduled
Warning to device	Send message with priority level to device

This list will be much more detailed in **D4.4 (Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim Report)** to be released in M18.

4.2. EXPLOITATION & SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

4.2.1. REQUIREMENTS FROM THE GRANT AGREEMENT

Article 28.1 of the General Agreement requires each of the project participants to exploit the results of the project, they have to take measures aiming to ensure this is done with its results (either directly or indirectly) by:

- (a) using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- (c) creating and providing a service, or
- (d) using them in standardisation activities.

4.2.2. INDIVIDUAL PARTNERS' INITIAL EXPLOITATION PLAN

BIMprove partners are organizations of different nature, there are research organizations, a standardization body, construction companies, a software company, a robot manufacturer and others. For each of these their optimal individual exploitation will be different, and for each of these a more detailed exploitation plan will be developed. In addition, potential joint exploitation post-project will also be investigated.

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Each of the project partners will further develop and refine their individual Exploitation plans and will be presented in **D4.4 Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim Report**) to be released in M18.

Table 11: Individual Exploitation Plan (Preliminary)

Individual exploitation plans	
SINTEF	SINTEF foresees BIMprove as a key enabling technology for the Norwegian construction sector. BIM is de-facto standard when it comes to publicly financed constructions but has a little market share in the private counterpart. SINTEF will be able to extend its knowledgebase with the results from BIMprove and implement it in the so-called SINTEF books, which is a knowledge source for the private and also the public market. The state-of-the-art technology used and developed in BIMprove will provide SINTEF with the necessary toolset and experience to deliver the commitment: "Technology for a better society".
ZHAW	For ZHAW, the BIMprove project results are extremely valuable and are used in the areas of research and development and in academic education. As Zurich University of Applied Sciences, we have the opportunity to apply the latest sensor technologies and the navigation of autonomous systems in a real test environment. With additional expertise we will gain from th project, we are able expand our knowledge and transfer it to other areas and disciplines (smart farming, human-machine cooperation, etc.). On national and international level we provide our knowledge to industrial and academic partners. As one of the biggest Universities of applied sciences in Switzerland we have extensive laboratories and transfer options at our disposal. The interdisciplinary know-how will also be used in academic training for robotics and civil engineering courses. Lectures and seminars will be offered at bachelor and master level that combine the latest developments in robotics and BIM and are taught to future engineers. Cooperative supervision of PhD theses is also possible within the framework of the collaboration between the Zurich universities as part of the canton's digitization initiative which was approved by the cantonal parliament in early 2020.
HRS	HRS expects to be able to automate control tasks on site, where qualified personnel are currently required to certify the correct construction / placement of each element on a daily basis. It also aims to improve its management system and overview of the current state of the work through new options, such as the positioning of its resources in real time and the ability to re-simulate on site depending on possible unforeseen circumstances. With the above, it is expected to improve efficiency, both in terms of time and resources
VIAS	VIAS expect that the outcome from BIMprove will help us to improve the productivity, reducing rework, it will let us to keep budgets in line, thanks to the reducing of conflicts and changes along the construction of a building, caused by the identifying of the problems in real time or at least in earlier stages of the constructions process. As well the continuous monitoring and training will help us to reduce the number of accidents, creating safety workplaces and minimizing working hours, which have a direct impact on the productivity in terms of time and cost.
ROBI	Robotnik as a European service robotics company is very interested in the exploitation of the robotic system outcome from BIMprove. It will be used to improve and enhance the capabilities of our applications in service mobile robotics. This system will allow the company introduce robotics in the construction sector where dangerous, repetitive and low value tasks are to be executed, improving our global market visibility and providing us great industrial relevance.

Individual exploitation plans	
VTT	VTT expects to deepen our understanding of human factors in safety-critical work tasks, which can open new research possibilities in the construction sector. The experiences of workers interacting with robots at a worksite will be valuable and enhance VTT's expertise on the safety of mobile robots and drones as well as human-robot interaction. Additionally, the AR/VR and wearable devices to be experimented with real workers in this project will enable VTT to gain user experiences of these technologies and further develop state-of-the-art user research methods for applied and safety-critical use contexts. Regarding the AI-related development work, VTT expects BIMprove to enhance and extend our competence and knowledge portfolio related to AI-based services in facilities management sector. In addition, the project will strengthen our capabilities to identify safety-critical situations and create situation awareness that is based on data collected from multiple heterogeneous sources and analysis of BIM models. This competence will be transferred into industrial use via contract R&D projects and software engineering consultancy projects, for example.
FhG-IAO	Fraunhofer's role in German society is to bridge the gap between research and the market. The participation in the BIMprove project will do both for FhG-IAO: open new research opportunities (together with its cooperation partner USTUTT-IAT), and create a unique selling point for consultancy and development projects with partners and customers in the AEC (Architecture Engineering Construction) sector. In Germany BIM is just now gaining traction in the architecture and engineering sector, which is why this sector has been a big part of the target customer group of FhG-IAO's Building Culture Innovation team. The team is aiming to broaden this target audience and look for more projects with the construction sector. The knowledge gained and the technology developed in BIMprove, especially the software architecture for digital twins, will help with this goal. To the same effect FhG-IAO will be able to exploit the user experiences of construction workers with the user interfaces developed in the project, which will be based on AR/VR and wearable devices, which to this day are not common on construction sites.
DIN	Standardisation contributes to the exploitation of the results by serving as a tool for implementing the results developed in the project.
CATENDA	Catenda provides the BIM-oriented collaboration platform Bimsync. We have several customers over the world using our software to collaborate in their construction projects. We believe that the technologies developed in BIMprove will strengthen our offering on the construction site. Our approach with a strong focus on open standards in construction (like IFC, BCF, bSDD etc) make is relatively easy to integrate this into the workflows we offer our customers through Bimsync. We believe BIMprove will in this way provide our customers, their construction sites and the workers and companies there with heightened efficiency and safety.
AUSTRALO	ASUTRALO will leverage the outcomes of BIMprove in its mission to bridge the divide between the high-tech Research + Innovation and the market. This will be achieved by exploiting the knowledge acquired in previous and ongoing projects with a focus on marketing services and ecosystem dynamization. Participating in BIMprove is an opportunity to contribute to the uptake and validation of the Digital Building Twins market, reinforcing and enlarging our portfolio of technical partners in advanced manufacturing and processing. This will allow the organization to expand our range of services towards other customers and partners, at European and international range.
AFG	AF Gruppen is a leading contracting and industrial group in Scandinavia. In order to maintain our leadership, we see BIMprove as a tool for our business to create value for our customers, owners, employees, and society at large. BIMprove is expected to contribute toward safe working environment for our employees and sub-contractor personnel, new services that help solve society's environmental challenges and ethical business operations that create security for our customers.

Individual exploitation plans	
USTUTT	<p>Taking part in the BIMprove project will extend the knowledgebase and deepen the understanding about digital building twins and therefore open new research opportunities for the Building Culture Innovation team at USTUTT-IAT. This knowledge and the application and development of state-of-the-art user research methods in the fields of user interface development, usability engineering und user experience testing will be used to position and promote USTUTT in further proposals both on a national and on the EU-level.</p> <p>Furthermore, USTUTT plans to exploit the knowledge gained and the technology developed by bringing it to the AEC market together with its cooperation partner FhG-IAO.</p>

4.2.3. EXPLOITATION DELIVERABLES & CONTENTS

D4.4 (Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim Report, to be delivered in month 18), will include a detailed assessment of the project footprint in terms of KPIs and exploitable assets in period 1, including contributions to standardisation. Overview of expected business models and sustainability measures.

At the end of the project, **D4.6** (Impact Assessment and Exploitation Final Report, delivered in month 36) will contain an evaluation of the impact created by the project, outlining the exploitation model followed and sustainability strategy proposed. This will include key exploitable assets, contribution to SDOs¹⁷, market readiness assessment and knowledge and protection management plan.

In addition, also delivered at the end of the project, is **D4.7** (BIMprove Asset Portfolio, in month 36). This will include a compilation of exploitable results achieved by the project, which created impact during its lifetime and with the potential to contribute for further work, research or innovations. This includes all peer-reviewed and technical publications, source code repository, open research data, educational material, and standardisation / open-source contributions.

4.2.3.1 *Scheduled plan of work related to future deliverables*

The following table is the proposed timeline presented in a Gantt chart:

¹⁷ Standards Developing Organization

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Table 12: GANTT chart of planned work in related to exploitation

Month (1-12)	2020			2021												2022												2023										
	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
Running month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36		
Overall project dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies.	x	x	x																																			
Deliverable 4.1				O																																		
Assesment of project footprint in terms of KPIs				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x																										
Assesments of exploitable assets in period 1							x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x																							
Contributions to standardization							x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x																								
Overview of expected business models																																						
Overview of sustainability measures																																						
Deliverable 4.4																																						
Evaluation of the impact created by the project																																						
Key Exploitable assets define																																						
Report contributions to SDOs																																						
Market readiness assessment																																						
Knowledge and protection managemnt plan																																						
Deliverable 4.6																																						
Exploitable results for further work																																						
Exploitable results for further research																																						
Exploitable results for further innovations																																						
List of peer reviewed publications, source code repositories, open research data																																						
List of educational material, standardization and open source contributions																																						
Deliverable 4.7																																						

4.2.4. TOOLS & METHODOLOGIES TO SUPPORT EXPLOITATION

4.2.4.1 Value proposition

BIMprove will seek to create value to each key actor, by emphasizing the unique selling points of the services created. **BIMprove** use the **Osterwalder’s Value Proposition Canvas**¹⁸ that looks at the fit of the new services between the needs and gains of the customer and the services’ gain creators and pain relievers.

Figure 12: Value proposition canvas

¹⁸ Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., Bernarda, G., Smith, A. (2014) Value Proposition Design: How to Create Products and Services Customers Want, John Wiley & Sons.

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4.2.4.2 Business Model Canvas

BIMprove proposes to use the **Osterwalder’s Business Model Canvas**¹⁹ as framework for the business plan. The plan delivers a “go to-market” strategy that ensures both the viability and sustainability of the services beyond the project final delivery. The partners will seek to explore monetization models for any spin off services that may derive from the projects. Different business models like direct exploitation by consortium partners, software licensing to 3rd party system integrators or open-source licensing models might be evaluated based upon detailed market analysis. The figure below depicts an initial approach to the business model canvas, however an updated version will be included in the dedicated exploitation deliverable to be submitted at M18 (**D4.4** (Impact Assessment and Exploitation Interim Report)).

Figure 13: Business model canvas

4.2.4.3 Impact Assessment

Detailed assessment of the BIMprove results will be evaluated against a set of defined KPIs. Two main areas will be looked at; 1) Performance of outreach measures that are implemented will be evaluated against the objectives of the project. 2) Benefits to the socio-economy of the different

¹⁹ Osterwalder, Alexander; Pigneur, Yves; Clark, Tim (2010). Business Model Generation: A Handbook For Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers.

geographical areas of the Consortium partners. These aspects will be documented in an impact assessment evaluation.

4.2.4.4 Market Technology Readiness Assessment

The market technology readiness assessment will be used as a project planning tool, that will include a detailed market analysis. The market analysis will consist of 2 parts, which are an external analysis and an internal analysis. Where the external analysis will look at trends and power structures for the intended market. Internal analysis will look at analysing different value creation activities that might derive from the services. We will also look at frameworks like Indicative Social Return on Investment (SROI): a method for measuring input, output, outcomes and impact factors that can affect the stakeholders. Valid strategies for market penetration and scale up strategies will be derived from the detailed technology readiness assessment analysis.

4.2.4.5 Market Analysis methodologies

For the market analysis we will use the following three frameworks:

4.2.4.5.1 External analysis:

1. PEST²⁰ analysis

The PEST analysis is a management tool where one assesses external factors that can have an impact on the implementation and operations in the market. There are four factors that one assesses. political, economic, societal and technology factors/trends.

Figure 14: PEST analysis

2. Porter's 5 forces analysis²¹

Porter's Five Forces is a framework for analysing the market environment. It consists of looking at power structure and threat assessments. The factors are bargaining power of suppliers, threat of

²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/PEST_analysis

²¹ Michael E. Porter (1980), "Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors"

new entrants, threat substitutes, bargaining power of buyers and industry rivalry. The figure below illustrates these factors:

Figure 15: Porter's five forces (1979)

4.2.4.5.2 Internal analysis:

1. Stabel and Fjeldstad's value network analysis²²

The value networks - a short form for "firms that can be modelled as value networks" - rely on a mediating technology to link clients or customers who are or wish to be interdependent. The mediating technology facilitates exchange relationships among customers distributed in space and time. The firm itself is not the network. It provides a networking service.

²² Stabell, C.B., and Fjeldstad, Ø.D. (1998) "Configuring Value for Competitive Advantage: On Chains, Shops, and Networks"

Figure 16: Value Network Analysis

5. STANDARDIZATION

5.1. STANDARDIZATION FUNDAMENTALS

5.1.1. TYPE OF STANDARDS

There are different types of standardization documents depending on their openness, their development time and their degree of consensus as shown in Figure 17: Types of standards.

Figure 17: Types of standards

A **standard** is a document that specifies requirements for products, services and/or processes. This helps to ensure free movement of goods and encourages exports. Standardization supports efficiency and quality assurance in industry, technology, science and the public sector. It serves to safeguard people and property and to improve quality in all areas of life.²³

²³ <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/a-brief-introduction-to-standards>

A **specification** is also a document that specifies requirements for products, services and/or processes. However, in contrast to standards, they do not require full consensus and the involvement of all stakeholders. Specifications are a trusted strategic instrument for quickly and easily establishing and disseminating innovative solutions on the market. A specification is the fastest way for turning research into a marketable product. Drawn up in small working groups specifications can be published within only a few months. These working groups are excellent for exchanging ideas with other market participants. Any specification can be used as a basis for developing a full standard.²⁴

A **de-facto-standard** is a technical standard that was not developed by a standards committee, but rather defined by industrial companies. A de-facto-standard can develop over the years as technically useful and sensible through the practice of many users and various manufacturers.

5.1.2. LEVELS OF STANDARDISATION WORK

Standards are developed by different standards bodies at national, European, and international level as shown in Figure 18 by the example of DIN.

²⁴ <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/a-brief-introduction-to-standards>

	Germany	Europe	Worldwide
General			
Electrotechnology			
Telecommunications			

Figure 18: DIN as part of the European and international standardisation structure²⁵

Therefore, interested parties, like manufacturers, consumers, retailers, universities, research institutes, authorities or testing institutes, send their experts to national standards bodies, like DIN in Germany. These experts are organised in Technical committees (TCs) and organise and carry out the standardization work in Working groups (WGs) and Sub committees (SCs).

If the standardization work takes place on European or international level, the national standards bodies send delegates or experts to work in the committees of the European or international standards bodies as shown in Figure 19.

²⁵ <https://www.din.de/en/din-and-our-partners/din-in-europe/european-standardization>

Figure 19: DIN's involvement in European and international standards committees (Delegation principle)

These processes ensure that the voice of each interested party of each participating country will be heard. Formal standards are the product of a consensus-building process of all interested parties to create a valuable basis for all users. This leads to a high acceptance of standards. Standards are voluntary and can be used by anybody. They only become mandatory if they are referred to in contracts, laws or regulations.

European standardization helps ensure the free flow of goods and the general functioning of the European internal market. The main goal of European standardization is to unify all standards that apply within Europe.²⁶

European Standards are developed by CEN, CENELEC (for electrotechnical standardization) or ETSI (for telecommunications standardization) according to the national delegation principle, with each country sending a delegation of experts to represent the national standpoint. This standpoint is developed in national committees that "mirror" the European committees. This way, stakeholders can work together in their own native language - a definite advantage. By taking on the secretariat of a European committee, national members can play a leading role in the committee's work. It is often decisive for national interests to be effectively represented at an early stage of the development of a European Standard. European Standards must be adopted, unchanged, as a national standard, and any conflicting national standards withdrawn.²⁷

²⁶ <https://www.din.de/en/din-and-our-partners/din-in-europe/european-standardization>

²⁷ <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/din-standards>

International Standards create a common technical language trade partners can use worldwide, providing a framework for the global market. They open up access to new markets and promote a free - and fair - world trade.²⁸

International Standards are developed by ISO, IEC (for electrotechnical standardization) or ITU (for telecommunications standardization) according to the national delegation principle, with each country sending a delegation of experts to represent the national standpoint. This standpoint is developed in national committees that "mirror" the international committees. This way, stakeholders can work together in their own native language - a definite advantage. By taking on the secretariat of an international committee, national members can play a leading role in the committee's work. It is often decisive for national interests to be effectively represented at an early stage of the development of an International Standard. The mirror committees also decide whether or not an International Standard should be adopted as a national standard - this is voluntary, in contrast to the European Standards, which must be adopted nationally.²⁹

5.2. STANDARDIZATION LANDSCAPE

5.2.1. COMMITTEES

For the comprehensive work on standardization it is highly important to have an overview of the standardization landscape in the field of BIM and Digital Twins. It is the only way to make sure that deliverables and results of BIMprove will address the right stakeholders and that custom-fit standards will be developed by and with the support of the responsible committees. First of all, the relevant standardization committees were identified. In the field of BIM and Digital Twins there are committees on national, European and international level.

On European level [CEN/TC 442](#) “Building Information Modelling (BIM)” is the most relevant committee to be considered in the context of BIM. It deals with standardization in the field of structured semantic life-cycle information for the built environment and aims to develop a structured set of standards, specifications and reports which specify methodologies to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record and securely handle asset data, semantics and processes with links to geospatial and other external data.

CEN/TC 442 forms liaisons with 18 ISO and CEN committees as well as with 15 further organizations namely Architects Council of Europe, Comité Européen de l'Industrie de la Robinetterie, European Ceramic Industry Association, Construction Products Europe, European Commission, European

²⁸ <https://www.din.de/en/din-and-our-partners/din-and-international-standardization/international-standardization>

²⁹ <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/din-standards>

Federation of Engineering Consultancy Associations, European Heating Industry, European Ready Mixed Concrete Organization, Euralarm, European insulation Manufacturers Association, Eurogypsum, Eurovent, European Construction Industry Federation and Small Business Standards.

- CEN/TC 442 consists of the following working groups:
- CEN/TC 442/WG 1 Terminology
- CEN/TC 442/WG 2 Exchange information
- CEN/TC 442/WG 3 Information Delivery Specification
- CEN/TC 442/WG 4 Support Data Dictionaries
- CEN/TC 442/WG 5 Chairperson's Advisory Group
- CEN/TC 442/WG 6 Infrastructure
- CEN/TC 442/WG 7 Horizontal role

Important standards for **digital twins** can be found in CEN/TC 442 as well as in [CEN/TC 247](#) **“Building Automation, Controls and Building Management”** dealing with standardisation of building automation, controls and building management systems and services for residential and non-residential buildings.

CEN/TC 247 forms liaisons with 9 CEN/CENELEC committees as well as with 5 further organizations namely European Control Manufacturers Association, European Commission, European Environmental Citizens' Organisation for Standardisation, European Partnership for Energy & the Environment and Eurovent.

CEN/TC 247 consists of the following working groups:

- CEN/TC 247/WG 4 Open System Data Transmission
- CEN/TC 247/WG 6 Electronic control equipment for HVAC applications, integrated room automation, controls and management systems

On international level the Technical Committee (TC) [ISO/TC 59](#) “Buildings and civil engineering works” and more precisely its Sub Committee (SC) [ISO/TC 59/SC13](#) **“Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM)”** is the most relevant committee to be considered in the context of Building Information Modelling (BIM). It focuses on international standardization of information through the whole life cycle of buildings and infrastructure across the built environment to enable interoperability of information; to deliver a structured set of standards, specifications and reports to define, describe, exchange, monitor, record and securely handle information, semantics and processes, with links to geospatial and other related built environment information; and to enable object-related digital information exchange.

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Members from 32 countries are actively participating in ISO/TC 59/SC13 (P-members) and members from further 17 countries have an observing status (O-members). Additionally ISO/TC 59/SC13 maintains liaisons with 20 ISO and IEC committees as well as with **buildingSMART International** and **Open Geospatial Consortium, Inc.**, since the topic of BIM has various overlaps with other areas of standardization. Therefore an exchange of information on a regular basis is essential in order to be up-to-date and to avoid unnecessary duplication of work.

- ISO/TC 59/SC13 consists of the following working groups:
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/JWG 12 Development of building data related standards
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/JWG 14 GIS-BIM interoperability
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/TF 1 Terminology
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/TF 2 Business Planning and Strategy
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/WG 6 Framework for object-oriented information exchange
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/WG 8 Building information models - Information delivery manual
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/WG 11 Product data for building services systems model
- ISO/TC 59/SC 13/WG 13 Implementation of collaborative working over the asset lifecycle

Important standards for **digital twins** cannot be found in one, but in several committees. In addition to ISO/TC 59/SC 13, [ISO/IEC JTC 1](#) “Information technology” and more precisely its subcommittee [ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25](#) “**Interconnection of information technology equipment**” as well as [ISO/TC 184](#) “Automation systems and integration” and more precisely its subcommittee [ISO/TC 184/SC 4](#) “**Industrial data**” including the working group ISO/TC 184/AHG 2 “Digital Twin” are of interest.

[ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25](#) “**Interconnection of information technology equipment**” deals with: Standardization of microprocessor systems, interfaces, protocols, architectures and associated interconnecting media for information technology equipment and networks to support embedded and distributed computing environments, storage systems and other input/output components; Standards for home and building electronic systems in residential and commercial environments to support interworking devices (IoT-related) and applications such as energy management, environmental control, lighting, and security; Cabling system standards for information and communication technology (ICT), in all types of residential, commercial and industrial environments for the design, planning and installation, test procedures, automated infrastructure management systems and remote powering.

Members from 29 countries are actively participating in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25 (P-members) and members from further 18 countries have an observing status (O-members). Additionally ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25 maintains liaisons with 29 ISO and IEC committees as well as with European

Commission, European Computer Manufacturers Association, International Telecommunication Union, United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, United Nations Economic Commission for Europe and Ethernet networks.

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25 consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/WG 1 Home electronic system
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/WG 3 Customer Premises Cabling
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/WG 4 Interconnection of Computer Systems and Attached Equipment
- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25/JWG 10 Industrial Cabling

ISO/TC 184/SC 4 “Industrial data” deals with standardization of the content, meaning, structure, representation and quality management of the information required to define an engineered product and its characteristics at any required level of detail at any part of its life cycle from conception through disposal, together with the interfaces required to deliver and collect the information necessary to support any business or technical process or service related to that engineered product during its lifecycle.

Members from 18 countries are actively participating in ISO/TC 184/SC 4 (P-members) and members from further 14 countries have an observing status (O-members). Additionally ISO/TC 184/SC 4 maintains liaisons with 35 ISO and IEC committees as well as with AeroSpace and Defence Industries Association of Europe - Standardization, ASM International, **buildingSMART International**, Dimensional Metrology Standards Consortium, Inc., Electronic Commerce Code Management Association, eCI@ss e.V., Ecma International, Energistics, Standard for the Exchange of Furniture Product Data, GS1, The International Association for Information and Data Quality, International Council on Systems Engineering, International Association of Oil and Gas Producers, Open standards for operations & maintenance, MTConnect Institute, NAFEMS Limited, North Atlantic Treaty Organisation, **Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards**, Object Management Group, Product Data Exchange using STEP, ProSTEP Association for the Advancement of International Product Data Standards, Small Business Standards, Uitgebreid Samenwerkingsverband ProcesIndustrie, Versailles Project on Advanced Materials and Standards and Web3D Consortium.

ISO/TC 184/SC 4 consists of the following working groups:

- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/AG 0 Change management advisory group
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/AG 2 Implementation Forum
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/AHG 1 Core Industrial data set of terms

- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/AHG 2 Nuclear digital ecosystem specification
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/JWG 16 Formats for visualization and other derived forms of product data
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/JWG 24 Use of IEC CDD for ISO data dictionaries and ontologies
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/PPC Policy and planning committee
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/QC Quality committee
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/TF 1 ISO 10303 SMRL architecture innovation
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/TF 2 SC 4 reference model for industrial data
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 3 Oil, Gas, Process and Power
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 11 Implementation methods and conformance methods
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 12 STEP product modelling and resources
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 13 Industrial Data Quality
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 15 Digital manufacturing
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 21 SMRL Validation Team
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 22 Reference data validation team
- ISO/TC 184/SC 4/WG 23 Vocabulary validation team

5.2.2. STANDARDS

In addition to the consideration of the relevant committees a survey of already existing standards and standards under development in the BIM and Digital Twins sector is important. Such a list of existing standards and standards under development allows for an assessment in which areas useful standards already exist and thus lays the foundation for a subsequent identification of standardization potentials and needs.

The research of standards and standards under development started with the identification of relevant keywords as well as known standards already applied by the project partners. The research was conducted by using the database Perinorm.³⁰ Besides standards of national standardization organizations like DIN the database also includes standards from the European standardization organizations CEN, CENELEC, ETSI and the international standardization organizations ISO, IEC and ITU. Using a keyword search option, a list of standards can be generated, which then can be downloaded in the form of an Excel file. An Excel template especially developed for the research of standards allows the presentation of a dashboard which gives an overview of relevant information around the results of the standards research as shown in Figure 20. The dashboard shows a list of general information (e. g. number of standards found or number of responsible committees) as well

³⁰ <https://www.perinorm.com/home/default.aspx?ReturnUrl=%2fdefault.aspx>

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as Type of Standards, Level of Standards and Active Countries and provides various graphics to support those. Additionally, it is possible to use the keyword search to receive a filtered list of suitable standards. The dashboard will be distributed in the BIMprove consortium.

Figure 20: BIMprove Standards Dashboard

The following keywords were provided by the project partners: *3D, 4D, 5D, Acquisition, Analysis, API, Applications, architecture, Artificial intelligence, Assets, Augmented reality, automated spatial data collection, Automation, Big Data, Layer System, Biocentration factor, Building, Bulding Information Modelling, Cloud, Collaboration, Construction Site, Constructions, Control, Cost, data acquisition system, Data Analysis, Data acquisition, data safety, data security, demonstrator, Detection, digital twin, Digitalization, Drones, e57, Efficiency, electrical risk, Electro-technical, Estimation, Extended Kalman Filters, Extended reality, falling objects, Fire and Health, Geolocation, Health, Health and safety on site, Human - robot interaction, human factors, human performance, Human-Robot Collaboration, human-robot interaction, human-system interaction, human-technology interaction, ICT, Improvement, Industrialized site, Industry 4.0, Industry Foundation Class, Information, Integration, Interface, interface design, IT security, layers, leadership, Machine Learning, machinery overturning, Management, Mechatronic Systems, Monitoring, Multi-Sensor, Navigation, On-site construction, Optimization, Photogrammetry, Pilot, Planning, Pointclouds, Reference Architecture, requirements, REST, Risk, Robot, Robotics, Safety, Scanning, Sensors, Software development, Specifications, statistics, summit-xl robot, system design, testing, tidying and cleaning, Time, twinning, usability, Usecase, user acceptance, user Interface, VDC, Virtual reality, Visual Odometry, Visualization, worker, Worksite, Zero Defect Manufacturing.* Based on these keywords a first search resulted in over 1,400 standards, specifications and standardization projects.

To narrow down this number to a realistic amount of entries it was focused on the **Top 5 keywords BIM, Digital Twins, AR/VR, GIS and Robotics**. Based on these keywords a second search resulted in approximately 100 standards, specifications and standardization projects. These standards relevant for BIMprove are listed in ANNEX 3: Standardisation including document identifier, full title,

status and remarks. They are categorized by level of standardization (international, European and national) as well as by the responsible committee.

5.3. STANDARDIZATION PLAN

5.3.1. FORMATION OF LIAISON WITH COMMITTEES

European and international Standardization Organizations propose liaisons to facilitate the collaboration between the standardization world and the research and innovation community. **On national (German) level** DIN has established an observer status with the German committee **NA 005-13 FBR “BIM - Building Information Modelling”** in order to receive information about ongoing BIM activities on European (CEN/TC 442) and international (ISO/TC 59/SC 13) level.

On European level^{31,32} all CEN and CENELEC committees can develop a project liaison with accepted research projects. This liaison allows a research project representative to participate in the meetings of the committees and relevant Working Group meetings as an observer. However, the participation from the research project representative is without decision power. Additionally, the project representative can propose a new work item.

On international level³³ all ISO and IEC committees can develop a liaison with other organizations meeting the following eligibility criteria:

- not-for-profit;
- legal entity (category A, category B);
- membership-based and open to members worldwide or over a broad region (category A, category B);
- competence and expertise to contribute to the development of International Standards or the authority to promote their implementation; and
- process for stakeholder engagement and consensus decision-making to develop the input it provides.

It will be distinguished between category A, category B³⁴ and category C liaisons. The liaison categories including purpose, participation as well as rights and obligations are summarized in Figure 21.

³¹ http://ftp.cencenelec.eu/EN/EuropeanStandardization/Guides/25_CENCLCGuide25.pdf

³² <https://www.cencenelec.eu/research/tools/projects/ongoingENwork/Pages/default.aspx>

³³ <https://www.iso.org/sites/directives/current/part1/index.xhtml>

³⁴ Category B is reserved for inter-governmental organizations.

External liaisons

Figure 21: ISO/IEC liaison categories

The expertise of the participants of CEN/TC 442 and ISO/TC 59/SC13 ensures that developed standards reflect the current state of the art and therefore experience wide acceptance in the BIM sector. A close cooperation with either CEN/TC 442 or ISO/TC 59/SC13 is of great advantage for BIMprove as deliverables of the project can be distributed European or internationally. Thus, it can be ensured that developed solutions will be applied in the BIM sector even after the project has been finished. Furthermore, the European role in standardization will be strengthened as developed results will flow into the standardization process, receive far-reaching acknowledgement and will become the state of the art early. For this reason, it is essential to strive for an active collaboration with either CEN/TC 442 or ISO/TC 59/SC13.

5.3.2. CONTRIBUTION TO STANDARDS UNDER DEVELOPMENT

All standards and standards under development are labelled with stage codes indicating the progress of work. The stages are presented in Figure 22. Depending on the liaison category, liaison organizations have the opportunity to comment on different drafts of standards under development in stages from 00 Preliminary to 40 Enquiry.

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Figure 22: Stage codes³⁵³⁶

On European level³⁷ DIN has access to active CEN and CENELEC Work Items via the CEN-CENELEC Projex³⁸ database. European standards currently under development in CEN/TC 442 are summarized in Table 13: European standards under development in CEN/TC 442. Further activities and ongoing work will be continuously monitored and provided to the project partners by DIN.

Table 13: European standards under development in CEN/TC 442

DOCUMENT IDENTIFIER	TITLE	STATUS	REMARKS
WI 00442023	Guideline on how to understand and utilize EN/ISO 29481 Building information models – Information delivery manual – Part 1: Methodology and format and Part 2: Interaction framework	Under development, Preparatory (20.60 Circulation of 1 st Working Document (WD))	BIM, information management
WI 00442024	Guideline for the implementation of BIM Execution Plans (BEP) and Exchange Information Requirements (EIR) on European level based on EN ISO 19650-1 and -2	Under development, Preparatory (20.60 Circulation of 1 st Working Document (WD))	BIM, information management
WI 00442027	BIM in infrastructure – standardization need and recommendations	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, infrastructure strategy,

³⁵ <https://www.iso.org/stage-codes.html>

³⁶ <https://boss.cen.eu/startingnewwork/Documents/StageCodes.pdf>

³⁷ https://boss.cen.eu/ref/IR2_E.pdf

³⁸ <https://projex.cencenelec.eu/>

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DOCUMENT IDENTIFIER	TITLE	STATUS	REMARKS
WI 00442029	Building Information Modelling – Level of information need – Part 3: Data Schema	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, data exchange
WI 00442030	Building Information Modelling – Level of information need – Part 2: Guidance for application	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, data exchange
WI 00442031	Framework and Implementation of Common Data Environment Solutions, in accordance with EN ISO 19650	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, information management
WI 00442032	Common Data Environments (CDE) for BIM projects – Open data exchange between platforms of different vendors via an open CDE API	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, data exchange
WI 00442033	Building information modelling – Exchange structure for product data templates and product data sheets based on ISO 16739-1 – Part 2: Requirements and configurable products	Under development, Preparatory (20.60 Circulation of 1 st Working Document (WD))	BIM, information management
FprEN 17412-1	Building Information Modelling – Level of Information Need – Part 1: Concepts and principles	Under development, Approved (50.60 Closure of vote)	BIM, data exchange
prEN 17473	Building information modelling (BIM) – Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of any built asset – Data templates based on harmonised technical specifications under the Construction Products Regulation (CPR)	Under development, Enquiry (40.60 Closure of enquiry)	BIM, data structures, Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)

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DOCUMENT IDENTIFIER	TITLE	STATUS	REMARKS
prEN 17549-1	Building Information Modelling (BIM) – Information structure based on EN ISO 16739-1:2018 to exchange data templates and data sheets for construction objects – Part 1: Data templates and configured construction objects	Under development, Enquiry (40.10 Start of draft translation)	BIM, information management
prEN 17632	Semantic Modelling and Linking Standard (SMLS) for data integration in the built environment	Under development, Committee (30.99 Dispatch of enquiry to CCMC)	BIM, information management
prEN ISO 12006-3	Building construction – Organization of information about construction works – Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information	Under development, Proposal (10.99 Decision on Work Item (WI) proposal, Accept)	BIM, information management, Digital Twins, standardised static Digital Twins, buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD)
prEN ISO 19650-4	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 4 : Information exchange	Under development, Proposal (10.99 Decision on Work Item (WI) proposal, Accept)	BIM, information management
FprEN ISO 21597-2	Information container for data drop – Exchange specification – Part 2: Dynamic semantics	Under development, Approval (50.60 Closure of vote)	BIM, data exchange Digital Twins, Semantic enrichment, organization and integration of heterogeneous Digital Twin data, Multimodal multi-models and Information Container for Data Drop (ICDD)

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On international level³⁹ DIN has access to active ISO and IEC Work Items via the ISO Projects⁴⁰ database. International standards currently under development in ISO/TC 59/SC13 are summarized in Table 14: International standards under development in ISO/TC 59/SC13. Further activities and ongoing work will be continuously monitored and provided to the project partners by DIN.

Table 14: International standards under development in ISO/TC 59/SC13

DOCUMENT IDENTIFIER	TITLE	STATUS	REMARKS
ISO/WD 12006-3 (previously ISO 12006-3:2007-04)	Building construction – Organization of information about construction works – Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information	Under development, Preparatory (20.20 Working draft (WD) study initiated)	BIM, information management Digital Twins, standardised static Digital Twins, buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD)
ISO/WD 12911 (previously ISO/TS 12911:2012-09)	Framework for building information modelling (BIM) guidance	Under development, Preparatory (20.20 Working draft (WD) study initiated)	BIM, information management
ISO/CD 19650-4	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 4: Information exchange	Under development, Committee (30.60 Close for voting/ comment period)	BIM
ISO/FDIS 21597-2	Information container for linked document delivery – Exchange specification – Part 2: Link types	Under development, Publication (60.60, International Standard under publication)	Digital Twins, Semantic enrichment, organization and integration of heterogeneous Digital Twin data, Multimodal multi-models and Information Container for Data Drop (ICDD)
ISO/CD 22057	Enabling use of Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) at construction works level	Under development, Committee (30.60 Close of voting/ comment period)	BIM

³⁹ <https://www.iso.org/sites/directives/current/part1/index.xhtml>

⁴⁰ <https://login.iso.org/portal/>

DOCUMENT IDENTIFIER	TITLE	STATUS	REMARKS
	using building information modelling (BIM)		
ISO/DTR 23262.2	GIS (Geospatial) / BIM interoperability	Under development, Committee (30.20, Committee draft (CD) study/ ballot initiated)	BIM, data exchange, GIS
ISO/WD 29481-3	Building information modelling – Information delivery manual – Part 3: Data schema and classification	Under development, Preparatory Working draft (WD) study initiated)	BIM, information management

5.3.3. INITIATION OF NEW STANDARDS

Depending on the liaison category, liaison organizations have the opportunity to propose an idea for a new standard.

On European level⁴¹ a new work item proposal within the scope of an existing committee^{42,43} as well as a proposal for new work not falling within the scope of an existing committee^{44,45} may originate from:

- a CEN/CENELEC Member;
- a CEN/CENELEC technical body;
- A CEN-CENELEC Joint Technical Committee;
- the EC or EFTA Secretariat;
- an international organization;
- a European trade, professional, technical or scientific organization.

Acceptance of a new work item proposal within the scope of an existing committee as well as a proposal for new work not falling within the scope of an existing committee requires for CEN:

1. 55 % or more of the votes cast (abstentions not counted) are in favour;

⁴¹ https://boss.cen.eu/ref/IR2_E.pdf

⁴² <https://boss.cen.eu/reference%20material/guidancedoc/pages/tcnewwi.aspx>

⁴³ <https://boss.cenelec.eu/homegrowndeliverables/propnewwork/Pages/default.aspx>

⁴⁴ <https://boss.cen.eu/startingnewwork/propnewwork/Pages/default.aspx>

⁴⁵ <https://boss.cenelec.eu/homegrowndeliverables/propnewwork/Pages/default.aspx>

2. the population of the countries of the Members having voted positively reaches 65 % or more of the population of the countries of all Members having voted (abstentions not counted).

NOTE: If a work item proposal is intended to be adopted in the active work programme of the committee, the proposal should preferably be accompanied by a first draft.

Acceptance of a new work item proposal within the scope of an existing committee as well as a proposal for new work not falling within the scope of an existing committee requires for CENELEC:

1. a simple majority of the votes cast (abstentions not counted) is in favour; and
2. 71% or more of the weighted votes cast (abstentions not counted) are in favour.

NOTE: If a work item proposal is intended to be adopted in the active work programme of the committee, at least 5 members confirming their commitment to participate actively in the work.

On international level⁴⁶ a new work item proposal within the scope of an existing committee may be made in the respective organization by:

- a National Body;
- the secretariat of that technical committee or subcommittee;
- another technical committee or subcommittee;
- an organization in category A liaison;
- the technical management board or one of its advisory groups;
- the Chief Executive Officer.

Acceptance of a new work item proposal within the scope of an existing committee requires:

1. approval of the work item by a 2/3 majority of the P-members of the technical committees or subcommittees voting, abstentions are excluded when the votes are counted; and
2. a commitment to participate actively in the development of the project, i.e. to make an effective contribution at the preparatory stage, by nominating technical experts and by commenting on working drafts, by at least 4 P-members in committees with 16 or fewer P-members, and at least 5 P-members in committees with 17 or more P-members; only P-members having also approved the inclusion of the work item in the programme of work [see 1.] will be taken into account when making this tally. If experts are not nominated on the form accompanying an approval vote, then the National Body's commitment to active participation

⁴⁶ <https://www.iso.org/sites/directives/current/part1/index.xhtml>

will not be registered and considered when determining if the approval criteria have been met on this ballot.

A proposal for work in a new field of technical activity which appears to require the establishment of a new technical committee may be made in the respective organization by:

- a National Body;
- a technical committee or subcommittee;
- a project committee;
- a policy level committee;
- the technical management board;
- the Chief Executive Officer;
- a body responsible for managing a certification system operating under the auspices of the organization;
- another international organization with National Body membership.

Acceptance of a proposal for new work not falling within the scope of an existing committee requires the establishment of a new committee and therefore:

1. a 2/3 majority of the National Bodies voting are in favour of the proposal; and
2. at least 5 National Bodies who voted in favour expressed their intention to participate actively.

5.3.4. DEVELOPMENT OF NEW SPECIFICATIONS

BIMprove always has the opportunity to develop a new specification. **On European level**⁴⁷ a specification is called CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA). A CWA is a deliverable, which may take various forms such as text file or computer code, developed and agreed by the participants in a temporary working group (CEN/CENELEC Workshop). It is designed to meet an immediate need, can be quickly developed and can be used as fast track to future standardization activities.

The stakeholder involvement is limited to those directly interested in the subject. There is no geographical limit on participation. Hence, participants may be from outside Europe. The direct participation of interested parties, the possibility to indicate the participants and their organizations in the foreword and the rapid development process offered by a CWA, are particularly attractive for European research and innovation projects, which have to deliver results within the limited duration of their project lifetimes.

⁴⁷ https://boss.cen.eu/ref/IR2_E.pdf

Although a CWA is developed outside the normal CEN/CENELEC Technical Body structure and does not have the status of a European Standard, it is important to ensure the coherence of all the different CEN/CENELEC deliverables in order to protect the credibility of European standardization. A CWA, therefore, shall not conflict with a European Standard (and a Harmonization Document for CENELEC).^{48,49}

⁴⁸ ftp://ftp.cencenelec.eu/EN/EuropeanStandardization/Guides/29_CENCLCGuide29.pdf

⁴⁹ <https://www.cen.eu/work/products/cwa/pages/default.aspx>

6. CONCLUSION

Communication, dissemination and exploitation in H2020 projects are structured to ensure that projects have an impact beyond the mere research outcome. To this end, **BIMprove** has developed the **Impact Master Plan** which outlines the most important and critical elements related to its communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, that have to be taken into account throughout the entire project lifetime. The current document is expected to act as a point of reference for current and foreseen communication, dissemination and exploitation activities while all mentioned activities will be continuously monitored and updated throughout the project lifetime.

Regarding communication and dissemination, **BIMprove** aims to publicise the outcomes of the project, in its different phases, to the right audiences in the right time to demonstrate the ways in which research and innovation are contributing to a European 'Innovation Union'. Communication activities will show our multidisciplinary European consortium achievements in scientific excellence and contribution to competitiveness. In addition, the plan has been made keeping in mind the multidisciplinary nature of **BIMprove** members, which allows them to reach very different and well targeted segments of the identified stakeholders. Some channels have been chosen to accomplish a wider visibility and boost the project throughout some of the most common means of communication nowadays, such as social networks, events, papers, conferences or email marketing. At the same time, public relations campaigns have been planned to keep all related stakeholders updated on **BIMprove's** progress and results. All of these actions must be done under the designed corporate image and by spreading the right messages, so that every communication released to the audience is coherent with the scope of the whole project. To make sure all of these procedures are carried out properly, a system of metrics has been designed to measure the obtained results and compare them with the previously set objectives.

Regarding exploitation, **BIMprove's** consortium will continuously monitor and evaluate project's outcomes, examine possible exploitation routes and identify the most prominent exploitation pathway for each of individual asset. Various possible routes, such as individual and/or joint exploitation, scientific vs commercial exploitation etc. will be examined in order to define the optimum way to go forward and generate impact, beyond the closed borders of the project.

7. ANNEX 1: Stakeholders Mindmap

8. ANNEX 2: Dissemination & Communication KPIs

Measure	Indicators	Targets
Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific research publications in international journals	10
	Peer-reviewed publications and presentations in international conferences	10
	Scientific and Technical Publications (e.g. articles, blog posts) (yearly)	20+
Events	No. of scientific events participated	30+
	No. of non-scientific events participated	10+
Project Website	No. of visitors (monthly average)	1000+
Printed Material	No. of hard copies (e.g. flyers) distributed	2000+
Social Media	Size of the online community (by the end of the project)	3,000+
	No. of impressions (monthly average)	500+
Videos	No. of videos produced	3
	No. of visits (by the end of the project)	3,000+
Newsletters	No. of newsletters contributed/released	9

9. ANNEX 3: Standardisation

International

[IEC/TC 100](#) *Sound, vision and multimedia systems and equipment*, Secretariat: JISC (Japan) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
IEC/TR 63308:2020-07	VR/AR/MR systems and equipment	Published	AR/VR

[IEC/TC 110](#) *Flat panel display devices*, Secretariat: JISC (Japan) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
IEC/TR 63145-1-1:2018-09	Eyewear display – Part 1-1: Generic introduction	Published	AR/VR
IEC 63145-1-2:2020-07	Eyewear display – Part 1-2: Generic – Terminology	Published	AR/VR
IEC 63145-20-10:2019-08	Eyewear display – Part 20-10: Fundamental measurement methods – Optical properties	Published	AR/VR
IEC 63145-20-20:2019-09	Eyewear display – Part 20-20: Fundamental measurement methods – Image quality	Published	AR/VR
IEC 63145-21-20:2020-07	Eyewear display – Part 21-20: Specific measuring methods for VR image quality – Screen Door Effect	Published	AR/VR
IEC 63145-22-10:2020-01	Eyewear display – Part 22-10: Specific measurement methods for AR type – Optical properties	Published	AR/VR
IEC 63145-22-20:2020-08	Eyewear display – Part 22-20: Measurement methods for AR type – Image quality	Published	AR/VR

[ISO/IEC JTC 1](#) *Information technology*, Secretariat: ANSI (United States) – Committee

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 24 Computer graphics and image processing, Secretariat: BSI (United Kingdom) – Sub committee

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 25 Interconnection of information technology equipment, Secretariat: DIN (Germany) – Sub committee

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29 Coding of audio, picture, multimedia and hypermedia information, Secretariat: JISC (Japan) – Sub committee

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 Internet of Things and related technologies, Secretariat: KATS (Korea) – Sub committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO/IEC 14543-3-1:2006-09	Information technology – Home Electronic Systems (HES) Architecture – Part 3-1: Communication layers – Application layer for network based control of HES Class 1	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO/IEC 14543-3-2:2006-09	Information technology – Home Electronic Systems (HES) Architecture – Part 3-2: Communication layers – Transport, network and general parts of data link layer for network based control of HES Class 1	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT
ISO/IEC 14543-3-3:2007-01	Information technology – Home electronic system (HES) architecture – Part 3-3: User process for network based control of HES Class 1	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT
ISO/IEC 14543-3-4:2007-01	Information technology – Home electronic system (HES) architecture – Part 3-4: System management – Management procedures for network based control of HES Class 1	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT
ISO/IEC 14543-3-5:2007-05	Information technology – Home electronic system (HES) architecture – Part 3-5: Media and media dependent layers – Powerline for network based control of HES Class 1	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT
ISO/IEC 14543-3-6:2007-01	Information technology – Home electronic system (HES) architecture – Part 3-6: Media and media dependent layers – Twisted pair for network based control of HES Class 1	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT
ISO/IEC 14543-3-7:2007-01	Information technology – Home electronic system (HES) architecture – Part 3-7: Media and media dependent layers – Radio frequency for network based control of HES Class 1	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT
ISO/IEC 14543-3-10:2020-03	Information technology – Home electronic systems (HES) architecture – Part 3-10: Wireless short-packet (WSP) protocol optimized for energy harvesting – Architecture and lower layer protocols	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO/IEC 14543-3-11:2016-02	Information technology – Home electronic system (HES) architecture – Part 3-11: Frequency Modulated Wireless Short-Packet (FMWSP) protocol optimised for energy harvesting – Architecture and lower layer protocols	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data protocols for building-specific IoT
ISO/IEC 14772-1:1997-12	Information technology – Computer graphics and image processing – The Virtual Reality Modeling Language – Part 1: Functional specification and UTF-8 encoding	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 14772-2:2004-03	Information technology – Computer graphics and image processing – The Virtual Reality Modeling Language (VRML) – Part 2: External authoring interface (EAI)	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 18038:2020-04	Information technology – Computer graphics, image processing and environmental representation – Sensor representation in mixed and augmented reality	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 18039:2019-02	Information technology – Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation – Mixed and augmented reality (MAR) reference model	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 18040:2019-05	Information technology – Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation – Live actor and entity representation in mixed and augmented reality (MAR)	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 18520:2019-01	Information technology – Computer graphics, image processing and environmental data representation – Benchmarking of vision-based spatial registration and tracking methods for mixed and augmented reality (MAR)	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 23000-13:2017-11	Information technology – Multimedia application format (MPEG-A) – Part 13: Augmented reality application format	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 23005-4:2018-09	Information technology – Media context and control – Part 4: Virtual world object characteristics	Published	AR/VR
ISO/IEC 30141:2018-08	Internet of Things (IoT) – Reference Architecture	Published	IoT

[ISO/TC 20 Aircraft and space vehicles](#), Secretariat: ANSI (United States) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO 14721:2012-09	Space data and information transfer systems – Open archival information system (OAIS) – Reference model	Published	Digital Twins, Long term access to Digital Twins data, Long term

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
			preservation and OAS

[ISO/TC 59](#) *Buildings and civil engineering works*, Secretariat: SN (Norway) – Committee

[ISO/TC 59/SC13](#) Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM), Secretariat: SN (Norway) – Sub committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO/WD 12006-3 (previously ISO 12006-3:2007-04)	Building construction – Organization of information about construction works – Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information	Under development, Preparatory (20.20 Working draft (WD) study initiated)	BIM, information management Digital Twins, Standardised static Digital Twins, buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD)
ISO/WD 12911 (previously ISO/TS 12911:2012-09)	Framework for building information modelling (BIM) guidance	Under development, Preparatory (20.20 Working draft (WD) study initiated)	BIM, information management
ISO 15686-4:2014-01	Building Construction – Service Life Planning – Part 4: Service Life Planning using Building Information Modelling	Published	BIM Digital Twins, Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)
ISO 16354:2013-03	Guidelines for knowledge libraries and object libraries	Published	BIM
ISO/CD 19650-4	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 4: Information exchange	Under development, Committee (30.60 Close for voting/ comment period)	BIM
ISO/FDIS 21597-2	Information container for linked document delivery – Exchange specification – Part 2: Link types	Under development, Publication (60.60, International Standard under publication)	BIM, data exchange Digital Twins, Semantic enrichment, organization and integration of heterogeneous Digital Twin data, Multimodal multi-models and Information Container for Data Drop (ICDD)
ISO/CD 22057	Enabling use of Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) at construction works level using building information modelling (BIM)	Under development, Committee (30.60)	BIM

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
		Close of voting/ comment period)	
ISO 22263:2008-01	Organization of information about construction works – Framework for management of project information	Published	BIM
ISO/DTR 23262.2	GIS (Geospatial) / BIM interoperability	Under development, Committee (30.20, Committee draft (CD) study/ ballot initiated)	BIM, data exchange, GIS
ISO/WD 29481-3	Building information modelling – Information delivery manual – Part 3: Data schema and classification	Under development, Preparatory (20.20, Working draft (WD) study initiated)	BIM, information management

[ISO/TC 184](#) *Automation systems and integration*, Secretariat: AFNOR (France) – Committee

ISO/TC 184/SC 1 Physical device control, Secretariat: DIN (Germany) – Sub committee

ISO/TC 184/SC 4 Industrial data, Secretariat: ANSI (United States) – Sub committee

ISO/TC 184/AHG 2 Digital Twin – Working group

ISO/TC 184/SC 5 Interoperability, integration, and architectures for enterprise systems and automation applications, Secretariat: ANSI (United States) – Sub committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO 10303-21:2016-03	Industrial automation systems and integration – Product data representation and exchange – Part 21: Implementation methods: Clear text encoding of the exchange structure	Published	
ISO 14649-1:2003-3	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control; Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 1: Overview and fundamental principles	Published	
ISO 14649-10:2004-12	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 10: General process data	Published	
ISO 14649-11:2004-12	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 11: Process data for milling	Published	
ISO 14649-12:2005-12	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 12: Process data for turning	Published	
ISO 14649-13:2013-03	Automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers –	Published	

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
	Part 13: Process data for wire electrical discharge machining (wire-EDM)		
ISO 14649-14:2013-03	Automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 14: Process data for sink electrical discharge machining (sink-EDM)	Published	
ISO 14649-17:2020-03	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 17: Process data for additive manufacturing	Published	
ISO 14649-111:2010-09	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 111: Tools for milling machines	Published	
ISO 14649-121:2005-09	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 121: Tools for turning machines	Published	
ISO/TS 14649-201:2011-12	Industrial automation systems and integration – Physical device control – Data model for computerized numerical controllers – Part 201: Machine tool data for cutting processes	Published	
ISO/DIS 23247-1	Automation systems and integration – Digital Twin framework for manufacturing – Part 1: Overview and general principles	Under development, Enquiry (40.60 Close of voting)	Digital Twins
ISO/DIS 23247-2	Automation systems and integration – Digital Twin framework for manufacturing – Part 2: –Reference architecture	Under development, Enquiry (40.60 Close of voting)	Digital Twins
ISO/DIS 23247-3	Automation systems and integration – Digital Twin framework for manufacturing – Part 3: Digital representation of manufacturing elements	Under development, Enquiry (40.60 Close of voting)	Digital Twins
ISO/DIS 23247-4	Automation systems and integration – Digital Twin framework for manufacturing – Part 4: Information exchange	Under development, Enquiry (40.60 Close of voting)	Digital Twins
ISO/PRF TR 24464	Automation systems and integration – Industrial data – Visualization elements of digital twins	Under development, Approval (50.20 Proof sent to secretariat or FDIS ballot initiated: 8 weeks)	Digital Twins
IEC 62264-1:2013-05	Enterprise-control system integration – Part 1: Models and terminology	Published	
IEC 62264-2:2013-06	Enterprise-control system integration – Part 2: Objects and attributes for enterprise-control system integration	Published	

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
IEC 62264-3:2016-12	Enterprise-control system integration – Part 3: Activity models of manufacturing operations management	Published	
IEC 62264-4:2015-12	Enterprise-control system integration – Part 4: Objects and attributes for manufacturing operations management integration	Published	
IEC 62264-5:2016-07	Enterprise-control system integration – Part 5: Business to manufacturing transactions	Published	
IEC 62264-6:2020-06	Enterprise-control system integration – Part 6: Messaging service model	Published	

[ISO/TC 211](#) *Geographic information/Geomatics*, Secretariat: SIS (Sweden) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO/DTS 19166	Geographic information – BIM to GIS conceptual mapping (B2GM)	Under development, Committee (30.99 Committee draft (CD) approved for registration as DIS)	BIM, GIS

[ISO/TC 299](#) *Robots and robotic devices*, Secretariat: SIS (Sweden) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO/DIS 10218-1 (previously ISO 10218-1:2011-07)	Robotics – Safety requirements for robot systems in an industrial environment – Part 1: Robots	Under development, Enquiry (40.60 Close of voting)	Robotics
ISO/DIS 10218-2 (previously ISO 10218-2:2011-07)	Robotics – Safety requirements for robot systems in an industrial environment – Part 2: Robot systems, robot applications and robot cells integration	Under development, Enquiry (40.00 DIS registered)	Robotics
ISO/TS 15066:2016-02	Robots and robotic devices – Collaborative robots	Published	Robotics

[ITU](#) International Telecommunication Union

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ITU-T G.1035:2020-05	Influencing factors on quality of experience for virtual reality services	Published (free of charge)	AR/VR

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European

CEN/TC 247 *Building Automation, Controls and Building Management*, Secretariat: SNV (Switzerland) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
EN ISO 16484-1:2010-11	Building automation and control systems (BACS) – Part 1: Project specification and implementation	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data Protocols for building-specific IoT
EN ISO 16484-2:2004-08	Building automation and control systems (BACS) – Part 2: Hardware	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data Protocols for building-specific IoT
EN ISO 16484-3:2005-07	Building automation and control systems (BACS) – Part 3: Functions	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data Protocols for building-specific IoT
EN ISO 16484-5:2017-07	Building automation and control systems (BACS) – Part 5: Data communication protocol	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data Protocols for building-specific IoT
EN ISO 16484-6:2020-04	Building automation and control systems (BACS) – Part 6: Data communication conformance testing	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data Protocols for building-specific IoT

CEN/TC 287 Geoinformation, Secretariat: BSI (United Kingdom) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
EN ISO 19107:2019-12	Geographic information – Spatial schema	Published	GIS
EN ISO 19115-1:2014-04	Geographic information – Metadata – Part 1: Fundamentals	Published	GIS

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
EN ISO 19115-2:2019-02	Geographic information – Metadata – Part 2: Extensions for acquisition and processing	Published	GIS
EN ISO 19137:2008-04	Geographic information – Core profile of the spatial	Published	GIS

[CEN/TC 310](#) *Advanced Manufacturing Technologies*, Secretariat: BSI (United Kingdom) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
prEN ISO 10218-1	Robotics – Safety requirements for robot systems in an industrial environment – Part 1: Robots	Under approval	Robotics
prEN ISO 10218-2	Robots and robotic devices – Safety requirements for industrial robots – Part 2: Robot systems and integration	Under approval	Robotics

[CEN/TC 442](#) *Building Information Modelling (BIM)*, Secretariat: SN (Norway) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
WI 00442023	Guideline on how to understand and utilize EN/ISO 29481 Building information models – Information delivery manual – Part 1: Methodology and format and Part 2: Interaction framework	Under development, Preparatory (20.60 Circulation of 1 st Working Document (WD))	BIM, information management
WI 00442024	Guideline for the implementation of BIM Execution Plans (BEP) and Exchange Information Requirements (EIR) on European level based on EN ISO 19650-1 and -2	Under development, Preparatory (20.60 Circulation of 1 st Working Document (WD))	BIM, information management
WI 00442027	BIM in infrastructure – standardization need and recommendations	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, strategy, infrastructure
WI 00442029	Building Information Modelling – Level of information need – Part 3: Data Schema	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, data exchange
WI 00442030	Building Information Modelling – Level of information need – Part 2: Guidance for application	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, data exchange
WI 00442031	Framework and Implementation of Common Data Environment Solutions, in accordance with EN ISO 19650	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of	BIM, information management

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
		Preliminary Work Item (WI))	
WI 00442032	Common Data Environments (CDE) for BIM projects – Open data exchange between platforms of different vendors via an open CDE API	Under development, Preliminary (00.60 Proposal of Preliminary Work Item (WI))	BIM, data exchange
WI 00442033	Building information modelling – Exchange structure for product data templates and product data sheets based on ISO 16739-1 – Part 2: Requirements and configurable products	Under development, Preparatory (20.60 Circulation of 1 st Working Document (WD))	BIM, information management
EprEN 17412-1	Building Information Modelling – Level of Information Need – Part 1: Concepts and principles	Under development, Approved (50.60 Closure of vote)	BIM, data exchange
CEN/TR 17439:2020-06	Guidance on how to implement EN ISO 19650-1 and -2 in Europe	Published	BIM, information management
prEN 17473	Building information modelling (BIM) – Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of any built asset – Data templates based on harmonised technical specifications under the Construction Products Regulation (CPR)	Under development, Enquiry (40.60 Closure of enquiry)	BIM, data structures, Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)
prEN 17549-1	Building Information Modelling (BIM) – Information structure based on EN ISO 16739-1:2018 to exchange data templates and data sheets for construction objects – Part 1: Data templates and configured construction objects	Under development, Enquiry (40.10 Start of draft translation)	BIM, information management
prEN 17632	Semantic Modelling and Linking Standard (SMLS) for data integration in the built environment	Under development, Committee (30.99 Dispatch of enquiry to CCMC)	BIM, information management
EN ISO 12006-2:2020-02	Building construction – Organization of information about construction works – Part 2: Framework for classification	Published	BIM
prEN ISO 12006-3	Building construction – Organization of information about construction works – Part 3: Framework for object-oriented information	Under development, Proposal (10.99 Decision on Work Item (WI) proposal, Accept)	BIM, information management, Digital Twins, standardised static Digital Twins, buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD)
EN ISO 16739-1:2020-02	Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) for data sharing in the construction and facility management industries – Part 1: Data schema	Published	BIM, data exchange, Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
			Digital Twins, Standardised static Digital Twins
EN ISO 16757-1:2019-05	Data structures for electronic product catalogues for building services – Part 1: Concepts, architecture and model	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data Protocols for building-specific IoT
EN ISO 16757-2:2019-05	Data structures for electronic product catalogues for building services – Part 2: Geometry	Published	Digital Twins, Augmenting Digital Twins with standardised dynamic data, Data Protocols for building-specific IoT
EN ISO 19650-1:2018-12	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 1: Concepts and principles	Published	BIM
EN ISO 19650-2:2018-12	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 2: Delivery phase of the assets	Published	BIM
EN ISO 19650-3:2020-04	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 3: Operational phase of the assets	Published	BIM, information management
prEN ISO 19650-4	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 4 : Information exchange	Under development, Proposal (10.99 Decision on Work Item (WI) proposal, Accept)	BIM, information management
EN ISO 19650-5:2020-07	Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM) – Information management using building information modelling – Part 5: Security-minded approach to information management	Published	BIM, information management

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
EN ISO 21597-1:2020-04	Information container for linked document delivery – Exchange specification – Part 1: Container	Published	BIM, data exchange Digital Twins, Semantic enrichment, organization and integration of heterogeneous Digital Twin data, Multimodal multi-models and Information Container for Data Drop (ICDD)
FprEN ISO 21597-2	Information container for data drop – Exchange specification – Part 2: Dynamic semantics	Under development, Approval (50.60 Closure of vote)	BIM, data exchange Digital Twins, Semantic enrichment, organization and integration of heterogeneous Digital Twin data, Multimodal multi-models and Information Container for Data Drop (ICDD)
EN ISO 23386:2020-03	Building information modelling and other digital processes used in construction – Methodology to describe, author and maintain properties in interconnected data dictionaries	Published	BIM, information management Digital Twins, Standardised static Digital Twins, Properties and quality assurance for buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD)
EN ISO 23387:2020-07	Building information modelling (BIM) – Data templates for construction objects used in the life cycle of built assets – Concepts and principles	Published	BIM, information management
EN ISO 29481-1:2017-10	Building information models – Information delivery manual – Part 1: Methodology and format	Published	Digital Twins, Semantic enrichment and organisation and integration of heterogeneous Digital Twins data, Information Delivery Manual (IDM)

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
EN ISO 29481-2:2016-10	Building information models – Information delivery manual – Part 2: Interaction framework	Published	Digital Twins, Semantic enrichment and organisation and integration of heterogeneous Digital Twins data, Information Delivery Manual (IDM)

ETSI European Telecommunications Standards Institute

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ETSI GR ARF 001 V 1.1.1:2019-04	Augmented Reality Framework (ARF) – AR standards landscape	Published (free of charge)	AR/VR
ETSI GR ARF 002 V 1.1.1:2019-07	Augmented Reality Framework (ARF) – Industrial use cases for AR applications and services	Published (free of charge)	AR/VR
ETSI GS ARF 003 V 1.1.1:2020-03	Augmented Reality Framework (ARF) – AR framework architecture	Published (free of charge)	AR/VR

National

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
DIN SPEC 91345:2016-04	Reference Architecture Model Industrie 4.0 (RAMI4.0)	Published (free of charge)	BIM
DIN SPEC 91350:2016-11	Linked BIM data exchange comprising building information model and specified bill of quantities	Published (free of charge)	BIM
DIN SPEC 91391-1:2019-04	Common Data Environments (CDE) for BIM projects – Function sets and open data exchange between platforms of different vendors – Part 1: Components and function sets of a CDE; with digital attachment	Published (free of charge)	DT, Semantic enrichment and organisation and integration of heterogeneous DT data, OpenCDE API
DIN SPEC 91391-2:2019-04	Common Data Environments (CDE) for BIM projects – Function sets and open data exchange between platforms of different vendors – Part 2: Open data exchange with Common Data Environments	Published (free of charge)	DT, Semantic enrichment and organisation and integration of heterogeneous DT data, OpenCDE API
DIN SPEC 91400:2017-02	Building Information Modeling (BIM) – Classification according to STL-Bau	Published (free of charge)	BIM
NS 8360:2015-06	BIM objects – Naming, type encoding and properties for BIM objects and object libraries for construction works	Published	BIM
NS 8360:2015/Veiledning	BIM objects – Naming, type encoding and properties for BIM objects and object libraries for construction works – Guide to NS 8360:2015-06	Published	BIM
SN/TS 3489:2010-09	Implementation of support for IFD Library in an IFC model	Published	IFC

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International

[IEC/TC 65](#) *Industrial-process measurement and control*, Secretariat: AFNOR (France) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
IEC 62890:2020-07	Industrial-process measurement, control and automation – Life-cycle-management for systems and components	Published	Life-cycle-management

[ISO/TC 176](#) *Quality management and quality assurance*, Secretariat: SCC (Canada) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO 9001:2015-09	Quality management systems – Requirements	Published	Organisational management

[ISO/TC 207](#) *Environmental management*, Secretariat: SCC (Canada) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO 14001:2015-09	Environmental management systems – Requirements with guidance for use	Published	Environmental management

[ISO/TC 251](#) *Asset management*, Secretariat: BSI (United Kingdom) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO 55000:2014-01	Asset management – Overview, principles and terminology	Published	Asset management

[ISO/TC 258](#) *Project-, programme- and portfolio management*, Secretariat: ANSI (United States) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO/DIS 21500:2020-06	Project, programme and portfolio management – Context and concepts	Under development	Project management

[ISO/TC 283](#) *Occupational health and safety management systems*, Secretariat: BSI (United Kingdom) – Committee

Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO 45001:2018-03	Occupational health and safety management systems – Requirements with guidance for use	Published	Health and safety management

[ISO/TC 301](#) *Energy management and energy savings*, Secretariat: ANSI (United States) – Committee

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Document identifier	Title	Status	Remarks
ISO 50001:2018-08	Energy management systems – Requirements with guidance for use	Published	Energy management

